

Citing this document:

GÓMEZ-NÚÑEZ, Antonio J. (2014). Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS 3): literature review and bibliometric analysis. CITEK Project Report, 71 pp.

Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS 3): literature review and bibliometric analysis

Abstract

Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS 3) arises as a core innovation policy to be developed and implemented under the new EU Horizon 2020 framework. This document mainly reviews academic literature in order to reveal some key points about RIS 3, namely, its baseline, relationships with other economic and business areas, leading researchers, or simply, implementation and analysis instances.

For the review, we have designed several specific queries to retrieve relevant and pertinent documents from Web of Science database. In addition, a browsing strategy was necessary to refine the different set of documents obtained. Also, diverse documents coming from grey literature, especially related to policy and decision making fields were included in the final set.

Finally, several tables and figures based on the information compiled were elaborated with the aim of offering an overview and a clearer idea of the present situation on RIS 3.

Introduction, concept and definition

Nowadays, innovation policies designed at region level have been a key approach for economic growth within European countries. Thus, European Commission has developed some instruments such as the *Innovation Union Scoreboard* (European Commission, 2013) which enables to analyse and assess the innovation degree of the different EU state members. The innovation degree is subsequently resulted in *Regional Innovation Scoreboard* (European Commission, 2012), a periodical report which offers a complete analysis about the innovation performance of EU state members and, accordingly, provides a classification of them into four groups:

1. Innovation leaders
2. Innovation followers
3. Moderate innovators
4. Modest innovators

For the period 2014-2020, EU has relied upon a new research and innovation strategy denominated 'RIS 3' (European Commission Joint Research Centre - Institute for Prospective Technological Studies, 2012) which is based on Smart Specialisation of EU regions by exploiting their strengths, existing resources and more competitive knowledge fields through an identification of their advantages and potentials as well as the establishment of well-defined strategic priorities. The concept of Smart Specialisation was created by a group of academic

experts (Foray, David & Hall, 2011) led by Dominique Foray in 2008 and has been successively addressed in further research works.

Foray & Van Ark (2007) noticed two main deficiencies in Europe to attract international R&D: 1) the fragmentation along national lines, which has constricted transnational flow and natural generation of centres of excellence; and 2) the emulation of successful strategies within EU regions and countries supported by national and regional public policies, which has resulted in knowledge uniformity, modest R&D centres and inflation of leading scientific- and technological-based industry. Therefore, it was necessary new and original areas of expertise to avoid a considerable waste of resources and look for a more coordinated “R&D system based on greater European-wide specialisation”.

Two years later, Foray, David & Hall (2009) took the instance of specific properties of General Purpose Technologies (GPTs) in order to design a flexible framework aimed at elucidating the logic of Smart Specialisation. Thus, the framework sets different strategies for *leaders regions*, which should focus on investing and researching about general purpose technologies, and *less innovators regions*, which are recommend carrying out applications from those new leader technologies instead. They state that “By so doing, the follower regions and the firms within them become part of a realistic and practicable competitive environment”. Then, they asserted that smart specialisation should not be understood as a simple strategy of the industrial specialisation of a certain region, rather as “a process addressing the missing or weak relations between R&D and innovation resources and activities on the one hand and the sectoral structure of the economy on the other” (Foray, David, & Hall, 2011a).

Therefore, it is expected that RIS 3 strategy becomes a cornerstone in the future of EU research and innovation policy in order to foster the cohesion, economic growth, development, entrepreneurship and competitiveness of the whole map of EU regions and countries.

Sources and Methods

At present, there are many scientific and academic databases which enable to search and retrieve science literature related to a specific field or area of science and knowledge, for instance, PubMed (Medicine), RePEc (Economics), LISA (Library and Information Science), etc. Although the most of these services are specialized in a specific field, there are some scientific databases with a broad multidisciplinary coverage and additional outstanding functionalities such as citation indices which enable not only to produce indicators on scientific output or collaboration, but also on impact. Thus, distinct services as Web of Science (Thomson Reuters, 2009), Scopus (Elsevier, 2004) or Google Scholar (Google, 2011) have successively arisen like interesting sources of scientific information to develop indicators, domain analysis or rankings, specially, in bibliometrics and scientometrics fields. Plenty of literature addressing their main features (time and subject coverage, number of indexed titles, citation window range , etc.) and even comparing some of these systems is available as well (Chadegani et al., 2013; Falagas, Pitsouni, Malietzis, & Pappas, 2008; Jacsó, 2005).

In this document, we have chosen Web of Science (WoS) database as the primary source for searching and retrieving documents on ‘smart specialisation’ topic, basically, according to some main reflections:

1. Currently, WoS is a very reputed scientific database of widespread use for academic and research community at international level. Thus, for instance, the most of the assessment and policy making systems have used WoS in order to get indicators and evaluation tools to support the decision making in public funding research. WoS is characterized by covering over 12,000 journal titles from all around the world with a broad multidisciplinary subject and time coverage.
2. Although Scopus covers a higher number of journal titles than WoS, in relation to our topic we founded a better coverage in the latter (See Table 1 below). This could be a consequence of the subject skewness which occurs in both databases and also, by the different journal assignment to scientific disciplines forming part of WoS and Scopus subject classification schemes.
3. A great majority of software supporting the production of bibliometrics outputs, such as BibExcel, HistCite or VOSViewer, among other, are thought to work on data directly downloaded from WoS platform (some of them also with Scopus data).

In addition to WoS, we used Google Scholar for seeking other document types excluded from traditional scientific databases, such as reports, working papers, non-impact journals and conference proceedings, policy briefs, etc., but quite relevant to the objective of this work, that is, to gain a deeper and clearer knowledge about the concept of 'smart specialisation' by analysing and revising its origin, development and the next future through a review of significant literature on the topic.

Due to the short life of the 'smart specialisation' concept properly, it was complex to design a search strategy providing a set of retrieval documents quite balanced regarding exhaustiveness and precision. Also, delineating the boundaries between what smart specialisation is and not, as well as its relationship with other adjacent concepts could result a difficult task because of the numerous allied topics.

Several *specific queries* including key terms related to smart specialisation and innovation strategies were launched against WoS database. Previous tests showed a high level of noise (non-relevant documents) when these terms were submitted in the field 'Topic' of WoS database. Consequently, key terms were used only in 'Title' field for the subsequent tests. No restrictions were imposed concerning time window and language while a refining by 'Business and Economics' area was applied.

Even so, a lot of documents retrieved through these queries were not just fitting the topic of 'smart specialisation' so a *browsing strategy* on the different sets of given documents was necessary. From selected documents, we could also use the automatic recommendation system provided by WoS database and the online journal platforms as Science Direct which enables to find new related documents on the basis of the citation patterns, that is, according to citation links given and received by each document. Table 1 shows a comparison of the total number of retrieved documents using the same queries in WoS and Scopus. Moreover, the subsets of documents after refining initial queries by subject area/s ('Business Economics' in WoS; 'Business, Management and Accounting' and 'Economics, Econometrics and Finance' in Scopus) is provided as well.

WOS	Total Docs	Refined	SCOPUS	Total Docs	Refined
Title=("innovat* strateg*") Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	772	369	TITLE("innovat* strateg*") AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI"))	621	219
Title=(speciali*ation AND strateg*) Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	71	22	TITLE(speciali*ation AND strateg*) AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON"))	59	16
Title=(speciali*ation AND sector*) Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	37	23	TITLE(speciali*ation AND sector*) AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI"))	35	19
Title=(speciali*ation AND cluster*) Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	20	10	TITLE(speciali*ation AND cluster*) AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI"))	23	7
Title=("strateg* of innovat*") Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	16	9	TITLE("strateg* of innovat*") AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON"))	14	9
Title=(speciali*ation AND econom*) Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	188	111	TITLE(speciali*ation AND econom*) AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "BUSI"))	151	65
Title=(speciali*ation AND geogra*) Refined by: Research Areas=(BUSINESS ECONOMICS) Timespan=All years. Search language=Auto	50	8	TITLE(speciali*ation AND geogra*) AND (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, "ECON"))	38	5

Table 1: Search strategies in retrieving documents on 'smart specialisation' in WoS and Scopus databases

Literature Review

In the words of Foray, David and Hall (2011) “the phenomenon of smart specialisation is not at all new; what is new is the analytical description of the phenomenon which generates a few insights and directions concerning policy making”. Therefore, it is clear that we are not dealing with a totally new concept, rather an evolution of previous ideas from a range of areas of economics, business, geography, development, etc. In relation to policy making, strategies based on ‘smart specialisation’ phenomenon have been included within innovation policies developed under the Europe 2020 Initiative for the Innovation Union. In fact, ‘smart specialisation’ could be defined as a type of innovation policy based on theory of regional innovation systems (RIS).

Moulaert and Sekia (2003) reviewed several territorial innovation models (TIM) and their main features, among them:

- Innovative *Milieux*
- Industrial Districts
- Localized Production Systems
- Clusters of Innovation
- Regional Innovation Systems
- The Learning Region

The increasing variety of terms referring to innovative activities within confined territorial areas encouraged to D’Allura, Galvagno and Li Destri (D’Allura, Galvagno, & Li Destri, 2012) to conduct an objective review of the main research contributions to the RIS field aimed at uncovering main topics and considered approaches through Author Co-citation Analysis (ACA) on RIS publications indexed in the Social Science Citation Index (SSCI).

As far back as 1992, Cooke used the concept of ‘Regional Innovation System’ in a study on economic regulation on the new Europe (Cooke, 1992). There, regulation is seen as a mechanism to support industry and increase its degree of competitiveness. Instead of central state, region is then considered as ideal spatial level for regulatory intervention. Different practices and evidences of regional innovation from Japan, France, Germany and UK (by focusing on Wales’s case) are exposed. Later on, Cooke, Gómez and Etxebarria (1997) translated the concept of innovation system from national to regional level and tried to define the key concepts of RIS. Then, the links between concepts of National Innovation System (NIS) and RIS seem obvious. However, in relation to the evolution of RIS notion, Cooke asserted that “the development path of the concept was almost entirely from regional science and economic geography” (Cooke, 2001).

Economic geography, defined by Krugman (1991) as the study “of the location of factors of production in space” is present in developing economic policies and strategies based on agglomeration and specialisation as well as their relationship and interaction (Ricci, 1999). Davis and Weinstein (1999) developed an investigation about the economic geography effects on a sample of manufacturing sectors of Japan which they compared to a previous study (Davis & Weinstein, 1996) based on a sample of OECD countries. They found that while economic geography has a low incidence on international structure of production, it becomes really important for understanding the structure of production at regional level. The Banks World Development Report’s (WDR) of 2009 promoted an active discussion among economists and geographers trying to reshape economic geography. Peck and Sheppard (2010) collected those comments and contributions in a new summarized publication. There, comments from

Deichmann, Gill and Goh (2010) pointed to the planned diffusion strategy in the policy road map of WDR 2009 which “aspires to fine-tune the ‘reshaping economic geography’ framework to a range of regional contexts”. In opinion of Beugelsdijk, McCann and Mudambi (2010) firm’s location is an issue of interest for scholars of (1) international trade and economics, (2) regional science, (3) strategy and international business, and of course, (4) economic geography, whose ‘traditional’ approach is focused on relationships between location and space. In contrast to this approach, the ‘new economic geography’ (NEG) has risen as a consequence of the inclusion of geography in the mainstream economic models. Besides, the role of multinational enterprises in reshaping economic geography was analysed.

At the same time, the influence of technology change and their continued expansion is conditioning the ideas on economic geography. Thus, while several researchers predicts the end of distance and geography distinctions due to globalisation favoured by technological and institutional changes, others arguing even for a more discriminative global economy, basically, at cities level (McCann, 2008). The development and growth of cities and regions was studied by Storper (2010) who refers to a combination of factors influencing it, among them, changing patterns of employment and specialization. Natário *et al.* (2012) believe that because of technological changes and globalisation, those regions trying to improve their competitiveness through innovation need a robust system of innovation at national, regional and even local level. Crauser (2002) considered really noteworthy the effect of the continued and fast advance of globalization together with the ever-increasing growth of technological change in affecting markets and binding the RIS to foster new regional policy transformations.

Also, technology expansion and globalisation have modified the role of location in global economy and competition varying from a competitive advantage in saving input costs to a new competitive advantage based on a “more productive use of inputs, which requires continual innovation” (Porter, 1998). Porter believes that innovation and competitive success in many fields are very influenced by geographic agglomeration, generally, through *clusters*, that he defined like “geographic concentrations of interconnected companies and institutions in a particular field”. Asheim developed several research works where RIS, clusters and their linkages and interactions were described (Asheim & Coenen, 2005a, 2006; Asheim, 2001). Karlsen’s opinion is that different authors and researchers have examined ‘innovation’, ‘specialisation’ and ‘agglomeration’ concepts from a different approach giving rise to three trends of thought: (1) ‘spatial economics – cluster analyses’; (2) ‘territorial agglomeration theory’ and (3) ‘path dependence’, which respectively focus on economic linkages, socio-cultural dimensions and the influence of the past (Karlsen, 2005).

Clusters are expanded over many places around the world contributing to the specialisation of regions and, subsequently, being a key element in leading regional economies by improving innovation and competitiveness of firms. There are a lot of academic and grey literature (basically, commissioned by policy making and decision making bodies) analysing cluster strategies over different regions, countries and areas of the world. Porter himself (1998) introduced some maps covering the most relevant USA and Portugal clusters. Edgington (2008) studied the new policies defined for Japanese innovation system and, among them, the regional technology clusters. Brookfield (2007) investigated links between firm clustering and firm specialisation in Taiwan and detected a machine tool cluster in Taichung area. Patterns of industrialization of China were examined by Long and Zhang (2012) who detected a greatly cluster-based process characterized by industries spatially concentrated, specialised and interconnected within several well-defined Chinese regions. In a study on regional innovation systems of rural and peripheral areas of Canada, Doloreux and colleagues (Doloreux, Dionne, &

Jean, 2007; Doloreux & Dionne, 2008) ascertained the development of a technological cluster in the region of La Pocatière, Québec.

Within Europe, cluster organization in Scandinavian countries, for instance, have been widely studied. Thus, Karlsen (2005), Palshaugen (2011) or Asheim (2001) analysed the dynamics and development of clusters in Norwegian regions. Also, Asheim and Coenen (2005b) reviewed regional clusters from different countries like Norway, Denmark or Sweden. Some cluster analysis have been developed by comparing European areas to some others world regions. Giuliani (2007) developed a comparative study of wine clusters from Italy and Chile with a similar profile of industry growth and modernisation. On his side, Schlosstein (2008) outlined the essential dimensions of two outstanding and clustered-based regional innovation systems, namely, (1) Bonwol Siwha Industrial Cluster in Gyeonggi province (South Korea) pretending to transform itself in a high-tech industrial cluster comparable to (2) Baden-Wuerttemberg cluster in Germany.

After reviewing literature dealing with clusters we have had the opportunity to appreciate that, cluster analysis is location-based and field-based, or in other words, working from a defined spatial or geographical location and focused on a sector of specialisation. In many cases, regions are proposed as location unit of cluster analysis. Some examples can be seen in works of Padmore & Gibson (1998) who proposed a overall framework for industrial cluster analysis in regions; Le Blanc (2000) studied spatial and regional growth patterns of the information technology industry in USA; on his side, Rosenfeld (2002) proposed a guide to cluster-based actions and strategies to be applied in less favoured regions in order to foster their cluster competitiveness. This guide offers a clear and descriptive disclosure of related concepts, barriers in clusters creation, actions to support clusters, etc. Besides, it describes what clusters are by means of some inherent features, such as:

- Clusters are based on systemic relationships among firms
- Clusters are geographically bound
- Clusters have life cycles
- Clusters are not defined by organisational membership
- Clusters produces externalities
- Clusters are defined by relationships

Up to now, we have addressed some key ideas feeding and giving rise to the relatively new concept of 'smart specialization'. The concept, originated within the European Union, it is expected to be implemented in the future EU research and innovation policy under the Horizon 2020 framework. The efforts of European Commission started with the assignment, creation and dissemination of core ideas through policy documents (Foray & Ark, 2007; Foray, 2009; Foray et al., 2012, 2009; Foray, David, & Hall, 2011b) and other information sources (European Commission Joint Research Centre - Institute for Prospective Technological Studies, 2012) aimed at supporting EU regions and countries in development and implementation of smart specialization strategies (RIS 3). Additionally, researchers from different fields of economy and business fields have begun to describe diverse experiences, practices and instances related to RIS 3, admittedly that the number of academic and scientific documents covered by databases as WoS or Scopus is far lower. Some of them are detailed below.

One of the first academic papers addressing the smart specialization concept was developed by Sandu (2012) in order to provide methodological and theoretical basis on smart specialization strategy and support its implementation in Romania. Later on, McCann and Ortega (2013; 2013b) conducted two studies dealing with smart specialization and its

interaction with innovation and the EU Cohesion Policy. Rusu (2013) describes the concept of smart specialization as a solution to prevent the misuse of EU research funds and to illustrate the concept development and its possible implementation within European and Romanian contexts. Although there is a general acceptance of convenience and chance to establish RIS 3 strategies, also some critiques have started to arise, such as in a research work of Camagni and Capello (2013), where a reviewed version of the RIS 3 dichotomy model based on core and periphery areas is proposed together with a new taxonomy of European innovative regions and new fitted innovation policies for the distinct regional innovation approaches.

Bibliometric Analysis

From our set of retrieved documents, we can elaborate some tables and figures supporting a better and clearer understanding of some topics linking to concept of smart specialization: the seed ideas about the concept, its interrelation with other science areas, the most relevant authors and publications, etc. Table 2, for instance, shows the most prolific authors of our document collection having produced at least three documents. In creating this table both first authors and co-authors were taken into account and, therefore, there is no distinction between these two roles in order to be a candidate to appear in the ranking.

Author	Num. of Documents
Asheim, Bjorn T.	9
McCann, Philip	9
Doloreux, David	8
Cooke, Philip	7
Foray, Dominique	6
Ortega-Argiles, Raquel	6
Rodriguez-Pose, Andres	5
Coenen, Lars	4
Hall, Bronwyn H.	4
Hall, Linda A.	4
Acs, Zoltan J.	3
Boschma, Ron	3
David, Paul A.	3
European Commission	3
Feldman, Maryann P.	3
Isaksen, Arne	3
Karlsson, Charlie	3
Parto, Saeed	3
Porter, Michael E.	3
Todtling, Franz	3

Table 2: Ranking of the most prolific authors in our set of documents

Similarly, Table 3 covers the most usual journal titles considered as a venue for publication of research works by these authors. In addition to denote author preference, normally, towards most prestigious and impact journals, we can get a relevant clue for uncovering some of the subject lines on which smart specialization is based. This is possible, for instance, through the analysis and study of scope and classification of the diverse journals. However, a lot of policy documents like briefs or working papers are available by other publication means distinct from academic and scientific journals (grey literature). Hence, it should be recall that information sources covering these document types are not being included in Table 3.

Journal Title	Frecuency
Research Policy	19
Regional Studies	14
Journal of Economic Geography	6
European Economic Review	5
European Planning Studies	4
Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society	3
Economic Geography	3
Industrial and Corporate Change	3
American Economic Review	2
Economic Modelling	2
Economic Systems	2
Economics Letters	2
Entrepreneurship & Regional Development	2
Environment and Planning A	2
European Urban and Regional Studies	2
Geoforum	2
International Regional Science Review	2
JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies	2
Journal of Evolutionary Economics	2
Journal of Technology Transfer	2
Journal of Urban Economics	2
Procedia Economics and Finance	2
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	2
Technology in Society	2
Technovation	2
The American Economic Review	2
Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie	2

Table 3: Ranking of academic journals used by authors

On its side, Table 4 includes the most cited documents of our collection, i.e. those surpassing the threshold of 300 citations received. As observed, the majority of these documents are not exactly addressing topics on 'smart specialization' rather related to economic geography and

innovation. The only a document containing the term ‘specialization’ in its title is the one ‘*Innovation in cities: Science-based diversity, specialization and localized competition*’ conducted by Feldman and Audretsch (1999). Hence, the first places in the ranking are for relevant and impact documents developed by well-known and recognised authors (Krugman, Porter...) in the field of economics and business. This fact might be due to some questions as (1) the skewness derived from WoS database coverage, focused on academic and scientific documents and (2) the novelty of the ‘smart specialization’ concept still in development and implementation within economic policy of, mainly, the EU and, therefore, without an enough background of specific literature to become a well-founded discipline.

Author/s	Title	Source	Year	Cited by
Krugman, Paul	Increasing returns and economic geography	Journal of Political Economy	1991	1,949
Audretsch, David B.; Feldman, Maryann P	R&D Spillovers and the Geography of Innovation and Production	The American Economic Review	1996	1,122
Porter, Michael E	Clusters and the New Economics of Competition	Harvard Business Review	1998	1,106
Morgan, Kevin	The Learning Region: Institutions, Innovation and Regional Renewal	Regional Studies	1997	606
Boschma, Ron	Proximity and innovation: a critical assessment	Regional Studies	2005	603
Malmberg, Anders; Maskell, Peter	The elusive concept of localization economies: towards a knowledge-based theory of spatial clustering	Environment and Planning A	2002	401
Cooke, Philip; Gomez Uranga, Mikel; Etxebarria, Goio	Regional innovation systems: Institutional and organisational dimensions	Research Policy	1997	363
Feldman, Maryann P.; Audretsch, David B	Innovation in cities: Science-based diversity, specialization and localized competition	European Economic Review	1999	356
Balassa, Bela	Trade Liberalisation and 'Revealed' Comparative Advantage	The Manchester School	1965	329

Table 4: The most cited document in our set of retrieved documents

The temporal distribution of documents of our collection can be observed in Figure 1, which depicts the whole range of documents over years of publication going from 1965 to 2013. A mere glance to the distribution allows detecting an increasing trend in the number of academic documents produced (in spite of some valleys in the distribution) over the last years, which reflects a considerable increment of authors’ production specially in the last six years. In general, as Price (1963) noticed, this may be considered the normal behaviour in science growth and, of course, his theory may also be extended to the development of news scientific disciplines or topics, where a baseline is the starting point to later foster a vast amount of new investigations and practices. The median of the distribution is 2007 meaning that more than

50% the documents are placed on the time period 2007-2013. Concretely, the highest number of documents occurs within this time and corresponds to 2011 that is the distribution mode.

Figure 1: Distribution of the number of documents over the publication years

In the last stage of our analysis, we have focused on the development of the ‘smart specialization’ concept, by examining possible research lines and science areas influencing on the creation and development of the concept. To do so, we have used the VOSViewer software. This program is aimed at visualizing of bibliometric data, specially, citation or text networks. Thus, from a text corpus or a set of documents downloaded from WoS or Scopus is possible to build a map based on frequencies and co-occurrences of significant terms extracted from title and abstract of documents. VOSViewer uses techniques for clustering and mapping the set of relevant terms according to their similarities and using its own algorithm. The VOSViewer developers (Eck & Waltman, 2010) consider their mapping technique as an improvement of Multidimensional Scaling (MDS), that is, a distance-based visualization technique where “the smaller the distance between two terms, the larger the number of co-occurrences of the terms”(Eck & Waltman, 2013). Also, is important to know that each term appearing in the map is represented by a circle and a label whose sizes refers to their significance within the whole text corpus, so that the larger are the labels and circles, the highest their significance.

VOSViewer enables to create four different types of maps. Here, Figures 2-4 corresponds to the three of these types of maps generated by VOSViewer from our document set. The first one is the denominated ‘Label View’ map displayed in Figure 1. As aforementioned, on the one hand, key terms are represented by circles and labels, being their size proportional to their significance or weight. On the other hand, the distances among terms point to their co-occurrence values. Additionally, a colour is assigned to circles according to the cluster where they have been grouped. Figure 2 shows four well-differentiated clusters that we can delineate through looking at key terms included. Thus, on the left side of the figure in red, we can see some terms like *geography*, *concentration*, *country* or *specialization* that we consider related

to 'economic geography'. The upper side of the figure is for a different cluster (in purple colour) addressing what in our opinion is 'international trade' as deduced from terms like *market*, *world*, *globalisation*, etc. Just below, in yellow, is possible to define a new cluster dealing with 'smart specialization & policy' including terms as *policy maker*, *r&d* and *smart specialization*. Finally, on the right side of the figure we can find a second big cluster matching with terms from 'regional science & innovation', namely, *regional innovation systems*, *institution*, *context*, *innovation policy*, etc.

All maps created by VOSViewer are based on the same basis but, however, each one has distinct purposes. Figure 3 covers the VOSViewer 'Density View' map whose main utility is to reveal the most important and populated areas of the map on the basis of its density, or in other words, according to the number of items and their weights in a certain area. Then, highest density points appear in red, while the opposite ones are expressed in blue. In this figure we can be perceived three main areas of density. On the left side, within the biggest cluster on economic geography there is a very dense area formed by seven terms: *specialization*, *growth*, *country*, *economic growth*, *european region*, *specialization* and *convergence*. On the right side, the cluster on 'regional science & innovation' include another widely dense area including terms as *regional innovation system*, *innovation system*, *institution*, *regional innovation policy* or *institution*. In closing, there is another smaller area of high density just in the centre of the figure. This central area results interesting because it appears interacting with the previous areas described. This area includes, basically three terms: *productivity*, *r&d* and *geography*.

In closing, we have introduced the last type of map generated by VOSViewer, namely, the 'Cluster Density View' one (Figure 4). This map can be considered as a hybrid proposal between the 'Label View' and the 'Density View'. Therefore, each cluster is represented by a different color and those cluster areas more densely populated will be highlighted in a stronger color. Oppositely, the lowest dense areas will be displayed in diffuse color. In opinion of VOSViewer' creators this view is especially interesting when clusters have to be examined separately by providing the most relevant terms and most relevant areas within a cluster. In our opinion, the three figures shows a very coherent representation of our document set and result in very nice tools in supporting and getting a more detailed perspective over the 'smart specialization' concept and its interrelation with other key concepts. However, the emergence of the term 'geography' in the centre of the Figures 2-4 has drawn our attention, since admittedly this term is included in cluster on '*economic geography*' it may be perceived as a core term influencing and interconnecting the rest of clusters. This argument is especially well underpinned by Figures 2 and 4.

Final Comments

It was not easy to establish clear boundaries about what 'smart specialization' is, i.e. seed concepts and ideas, through the scientific and academic literature covered by WoS. The complexity of the concept has been recently remarked by authors as Rusu (2013) or Sandu (2012). Thus, the latter asserted: "Given the novelty and complexity of this concept, more theoretical and methodological consideration should be given to further concept clarification, for the use of policy makers and for its effective implementation in various countries, each of them with its R&D and innovation background and economic context." Nevertheless, by analyzing our set of documents we could uncover four solid research lines: 'economic geography', 'international trade', 'smart specialization and policy' and 'regional science and innovation' dealing with concepts as clusters, policy making, innovation policies and systems, globalization, specialization, etc.

Despite the possible bias derived from questions related to, for instance, searching and retrieving academic literature from WoS database, WoS subject coverage, or query delineation and design, the several tables and figures provide consistent and solid results. In a way, we have been able to compensate this problem by adding documents coming from grey literature and covering diverse document types as policy briefs, working papers, or technical reports. Therefore, we think that, finally, we have compiled a relevant and noteworthy enough set of documents dealing with the concept of 'smart specialization' and allied notions which proved helpful in determining its origin, overlapping, development or implementation.

We think that more concrete information about citation and impact of scientific and academic publications addressing with 'smart specialization' concept would be desirable and useful in order to facilitate the selection of core and relevant documents from the point of view of the research and academic community. However, the novelty of the concept as well as the lack of a consolidated theoretical framework make difficult to get this information up to date. It also seems that because of European commission is the main driving force in launching and promoting this strategy a lot of the theoretical documents are generated in specific formats used there (policy briefs, working papers, technical reports...). Hence, these document types are not being covered by scientific databases, which have adopted other research document formats (original articles, conference proceedings, reviews, letters...). Other times, these documents have simply been not published in peer-reviewed journals or impact sources. In closing, it is obvious that despite the document set compiled in this document resulted comprehensive and appropriate enough, supplementary and further documents can we added with the aim of completing and enriching the final collection.

Bibliographic references

- Asheim, B. T. (2001). Localized Learning, Innovation and Regional Clusters. In Å. Mariussen (Ed.), *Cluster Policies – Cluster Development? (Nordregio 2001:2), Report* (pp. 39–58). Stockholm.
- Asheim, B. T., & Coenen, L. (2005a). Knowledge bases and regional innovation systems: Comparing Nordic clusters. *Research Policy*, *34*(8), 1173–1190. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2005.03.013
- Asheim, B. T., & Coenen, L. (2005b). Knowledge bases and regional innovation systems: Comparing Nordic clusters. *Research Policy*, *34*(8), 1173–1190. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2005.03.013
- Asheim, B. T., & Coenen, L. (2006). Contextualising Regional Innovation Systems in a Globalising Learning Economy: On Knowledge Bases and Institutional Frameworks. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, *31*(1), 163–173. doi:10.1007/s10961-005-5028-0
- Beugelsdijk, S., McCann, P., & Mudambi, R. (2010). Introduction: Place, space and organization - economic geography and the multinational enterprise. *Journal of Economic Geography*, *10*(4), 485–493. doi:10.1093/jeg/lbq018
- Blanc, G. Le. (2000). Regional Specialization, Local Externalities and Clustering in Information Technology Industries. In *40th ERSA Congress (European Regional Science Association). Barcelona, August 29 - September 1, 2000* (pp. 1–23). Barcelona, Spain: European Regional Science Association.
- Brookfield, J. (2007). Firm Clustering and Specialization: A Study of Taiwan's Machine Tool Industry. *Small Business Economics*, *30*(4), 405–422. doi:10.1007/s11187-007-9047-0
- Camagni, R., & Capello, R. (2013). Regional Innovation Patterns and the EU Regional Policy Reform : Toward Smart Innovation Policies. *Growth and Change*, *44*(2), 355–389. doi:10.1111/grow.12012
- Chadegani, A. A., Salehi, H., Yunus, M. M., Farhadi, H., Fooladi, M., Farhadi, M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2013). A Comparison between Two Main Academic Literature Collections: Web of Science and Scopus Databases. *Asian Social Science*, *9*(5), 18–26. doi:10.5539/ass.v9n5p18
- Cooke, P. (1992). Regional innovation systems: Competitive regulation in the new Europe. *Geoforum*, *23*(3), 365–382. doi:10.1016/0016-7185(92)90048-9
- Cooke, P. (2001). Regional Innovation Systems, Clusters, and the Knowledge Economy. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, *10*(4), 945–974. doi:10.1093/icc/10.4.945
- Cooke, P., Gomez Uranga, M., & Etxebarria, G. (1997). Regional innovation systems: Institutional and organisational dimensions. *Research Policy*, *26*(4-5), 475–491.

- Crauser, G. (2002). Good Practice Lessons from RIS+ Projects (2000–2002): Regional Innovation Strategies Under the European Regional Development Fund, Innovative Actions 2000–2002. Brussels. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/archive/innovation/pdf/guide_ris_final.pdf
- D'Allura, G. M., Galvagno, M., & Li Destri, A. M. (2012). Regional Innovation Systems: A Literature Review. *Business Systems Review*, 1(1), 139–156. doi:10.7350/BSR.A12.2012
- Davis, D. R., & Weinstein, D. E. (1996). Does economic geography matter for international specialization? Cambridge, Massachusetts. Retrieved from http://www.nber.org/papers/w5706.pdf?new_window=1
- Davis, D. R., & Weinstein, D. E. (1999). Economic geography and regional production structure: an empirical investigation. *European Economic Review*, 43, 379–407.
- Deichmann, U., Gill, I., & Goh, C. C. (2010). World Development Report 2009: A Practical Economic Geography. *Economic Geography*, 86(4), 371–380.
- Doloreux, D., & Dionne, S. (2008). Is regional innovation system development possible in peripheral regions? Some evidence from the case of La Pocatière, Canada. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 20(3), 259–283. doi:10.1080/08985620701795525
- Doloreux, D., Dionne, S., & Jean, B. (2007). The Evolution of an Innovation System in a Rural Area: The Case of La Pocatière, Québec. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 31(1), 146–167. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2427.2007.00707.x
- Eck, N. J. Van, & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538. doi:10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3
- Eck, N. J. Van, & Waltman, L. (2013). VOSviewer Manual. 1 January 2013. Retrieved from http://www.vosviewer.com/documentation/Manual_VOSviewer_1.5.4.pdf
- Edgington, D. W. (2008). The Japanese Innovation System: University–Industry Linkages, Small Firms and Regional Technology Clusters. *Prometheus: Critical Studies in Innovation*, 26(1), 1–19. doi:10.1080/08109020701846009
- Elsevier. (2004). Scopus. Retrieved May 30, 2013, from <http://www.scopus.com/home.url>
- European Commission. (2012). Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2012. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/innovation/files/ris-2012_en.pdf
- European Commission. (2013). Innovation Union Scoreboard 2013. doi:10.2769/72530
- European Commission Joint Research Centre - Institute for Prospective Technological Studies. (2012). Smart Specialization Platform (S3). Retrieved January 21, 2014, from <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/home>

- Falagas, M. E., Pitsouni, E. I., Malietzis, G. A., & Pappas, G. (2008). Comparison of PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar: strengths and weaknesses. *The FASEB Journal*, 22, 338–342.
- Feldman, M. P., & Audretsch, D. B. (1999). Innovation in cities: Science-based diversity, specialization and localized competition. *European Economic Review*, 43(2), 409–429.
- Foray, D. (2009). Understanding “smart specialisation.” In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van (eds. . Bavel (Eds.), *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications* (pp. 14–26). Retrieved from <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>
- Foray, D., & Ark, B. Van. (2007). Smart specialisation in a truly integrated research area is the key to attracting more R&D to Europe.
- Foray, D., David, P. A., & Hall, B. (2009). Smart Specialisation – The Concept. *Knowledge Economists Policy Brief n ° 9*, (June), 1–5. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/kfg_policy_brief_no9.pdf
- Foray, D., David, P. A., & Hall, B. H. (2011a). Smart specialization: from academic idea to political instrument, the surprising career of a concept and the difficulties involved in its implementation. Lausanne, Switzerland.
- Foray, D., David, P. A., & Hall, B. H. (2011b). Smart specialization From academic idea to political instrument , the surprising career of a concept and the difficulties involved in its implementation.
- Foray, D., Goddard, J., Goenaga Beldarrain, X., Landabaso, M., McCann, P., Morgan, K., ... Ortega-Argilés, R. (2012). *Guide to research and innovation strategies for smart specialisation (RIS 3)* (p. 114). Retrieved from http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/c/document_library/get_file?uuid=e50397e3-f2b1-4086-8608-7b86e69e8553
- Giuliani, E. (2007). The selective nature of knowledge networks in clusters: evidence from the wine industry. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 7(2), 139–168. doi:10.1093/jeg/lbl014
- Google. (2011). Google Scholar. Retrieved January 21, 2014, from <http://scholar.google.com/>
- Jacsó, P. (2005). As we may search – Comparison of major features of the Web of Science , Scopus , and Google Scholar citation-based and citation-enhanced databases. *Current Science*, 89(9), 1537–1547.
- Karlsen, A. (2005). The dynamics of regional specialization and cluster formation: dividing trajectories of maritime industries in two Norwegian regions. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 17(5), 313–338. doi:10.1080/08985620500247702
- Krugman, P. (1991). Increasing returns and economic geography. *Journal of Political Economy*, 99(3), 483–499. Retrieved from http://www.princeton.edu/pr/pictures/g-k/krugman/krugman-increasing_returns_1991.pdf

- Long, C., & Zhang, X. (2012). Patterns of China's industrialization: Concentration, specialization, and clustering. *China Economic Review*, 23(3), 593–612.
doi:10.1016/j.chieco.2011.09.002
- McCann, P. (2008). Globalization and economic geography: the world is curved, not flat. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 1(3), 351–370.
doi:10.1093/cjres/rsn002
- McCann, P., & Ortega-Argiles, R. (2013). Transforming European regional policy: a results-driven agenda and smart specialization. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 29(2), 405–431. doi:10.1093/oxrep/grt021
- McCann, P., & Ortega-Argilés, R. (2013). Smart Specialization, Regional Growth and Applications to European Union Cohesion Policy. *Regional Studies, Published*, 1–12.
doi:10.1080/00343404.2013.799769
- Moulaert, F., & Sekia, F. (2003). Territorial Innovation Models: A Critical Survey. *Regional Studies*, 37(3), 289–302. doi:10.1080/0034340032000065442
- Natário, M., Braga, A., Couto, J., & Tiago, T. (2012). Territorial Standards for Innovation: Analysis for the Regions of Portugal. *Revista de Estudios Regionales* 9, 95, 15–38.
- Padmore, T., & Gibson, H. (1998). Modelling systems of innovation : II . A framework for industrial cluster analysis in regions, 625–641.
- Pålshaugen, Ø. (2011). Research in action: The development of cluster specific innovation strategies in the Oslo region. In *Learning Regional Innovation: Scandinavian Models* (pp. 120–149). London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Peck, J., & Sheppard, E. (2010). Worlds Apart? Engaging with the World Development Report 2009: Reshaping Economic Geography. *Economic Geography*, 86(4), 331–340.
doi:10.1111/j.1944-8287.2010.01093.x
- Porter, M. E. (1998). Clusters and the New Economics of Competition. *Harvard Business Review*, Nov.-Dec., 77–90.
- Price, D. J. de S. (1963). *Little Science, Big Science* (p. 118). New York: Columbia University Press.
- Ricci, L. A. (1999). Economic geography and comparative advantage: Agglomeration versus specialization. *European Economic Review*, 43(2), 357–377.
- Rosenfeld, S. A. (2002). *Creating Smart Systems: A guide to cluster strategies in less favoured regions* (p. 35). Retrieved from
http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/archive/innovation/pdf/guide_rosenfeld_final.pdf
- Rusu, M. (2013). Smart Specialization a Possible Solution to the New Global Challenges. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 6(13), 128–136. doi:10.1016/S2212-5671(13)00124-X

- Sandu, S. (2012). Smart Specialization Concept and the Status of Its Implementation in Romania. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 3, 236–242. doi:10.1016/S2212-5671(12)00146-3
- Schlossstein, D. F., & Yun, J. J. (2008). Innovation cluster characteristics of Baden-Wuerttemberg and Gyeonggi-Do. *Asian Journal of Technology Innovation*, 16(2), 83–112. doi:10.1080/19761597.2008.9668658
- Storper, M. (2010). Why do regions develop and change? The challenge for geography and economics. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 11(2), 333–346. doi:10.1093/jeg/lbq033
- Thomson Reuters. (2009). Web of Science. Retrieved September 01, 2013, from <http://thomsonreuters.com/web-of-science/>

Annex I: Full Bibliography on Smart Specialization (RIS 3) and allied topics

Acs, Z.J., FitzRoy, F.R. & Smith, I., 2002. High-technology employment and R&D in cities: heterogeneity vs. specialization. *Annals of Regional Science*, 36, pp.373–386.

Abstract: This paper uses data from high technology industry clusters in U.S. cities to establish a strong positive relationship between city, industry (and university) R&D and subsequent employment in the same industry and city. Perhaps surprisingly, in view of recent results that heterogeneity favors growth, we found no evidence for spillovers from R&D in any one high technology cluster to employment in any other. However, spillover benefits from specialization appear microeconomically plausible in our context, though the data panel is too short to obtain any conclusions regarding growth.

Acs, Z.J. & Stough, R.R. eds., 2008. *Public Policy in an Entrepreneurial Economy: Creating the Conditions for Business Growth*, New York: Springer-Verlag.

Aiginger, K. & Rossi-Hansberg, E., 2006. Specialization and concentration: a note on theory and evidence. *Empirica*, 33, pp.255–266.

Alcorta, L. & Peres, W., 1998. Innovation systems and technological specialization in Latin America and the Caribbean. *Research Policy*, 26(7-8), pp.857–881. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S004873339700067X>.

Abstract: This paper examines the National Systems of Innovation (NSI) of Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) countries and attempts to assess their performances. Although it points out at a number of specific successes, overall, the region's NSI have evolved since their inception in the 1950s into weak entities. Science and technology institutions and organisations are not fully performing an enabling role; links and interactions between government support organisations, businesses and academia are tenuous; investment in intangibles and human capital is low; and, public policy is only partially effective. The main result of such weakness is that LAC countries' innovative performance has, as measured by the index of the technological specialisation (ITS), which relates the world's normalised shares of high- to low-tech exports, with the only exception perhaps of Mexico, remained stagnant or has fallen and has lost relatively to many countries that started at similar levels twenty years ago.

Algieri, B., Aquino, A. & Succurro, M., 2011. Going "green": trade specialisation dynamics in the solar photovoltaic sector. *Energy Policy*, 39(11), pp.7275–7283. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S030142151100646X> [Accessed December 16, 2013].

Abstract: The present study aims at providing a comprehensive analysis of trade flows and the domestic value creation of the major solar photovoltaic industry at the world level. Solar technologies convert light and heat from the sun into useful energy. The use of the sun's energy can not only reduce the consumption of conventional fuels, thus reducing the emission of detrimental greenhouse gases, but it can also enable a gain in enhanced fuel and energy security along with lessening costs. In addition, green technologies and industries can promote economic growth and international competitiveness, and can offer new business and employment opportunities. It becomes, therefore, extremely important to deeply explore the dynamics of the solar photovoltaic sector. Specifically, the present work analyses the main global trends of this sector and sketches the key players on the world market, including producers, installers, and top traders. Based on an analysis of trade flows at the 6-digit level, the international specialisation patterns are investigated, and the role of various market and trade drivers, including subsidies in the uptake of solar technologies, is identified and examined.

Andersson, G., 2012. Rethinking Regional Innovation. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 26(1), pp.99–110. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11213-012-9265-5> [Accessed January 17, 2014].

Abstract: Regional Innovation Systems (RIS) are understood as a loose alliance of private and public interests, governmental institutions, enterprises and other organizations. RIS are believed to be the cause for the increased competitiveness and productivity in the region. This article challenges the initial rationale and explores an alternative rationale on regional innovation, questioning if the relationship is the other way round: Does the workplace innovation and enterprise development assemble the regional innovation system? The findings introduce the heterogeneity of an enterprise development project at the same time embedded in the concreteness of the workplace innovations and extended beyond the organizational boundaries of the enterprise and the region. The discussions introduce a new and simultaneous rationality of innovation. The contributions to increase competitiveness and productivity become the source of an innovation system and not the result of the regional innovation system. The loose alliance in the innovation system becomes an effect, and not the source, of the efforts to increase competitiveness and productivity.

Andersson, M. & Karlsson, C., 2006. Regional Innovation Systems in Small and Medium-Sized Regions. In B. Johansson, C. Karlsson, & R. Stough, eds. *The Emerging Digital Economy: Entrepreneurship, Clusters, and Policy*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, pp. 55–81.

Abstract: Continuous product and process innovations are prerequisites for sustainable competitiveness of both nations and regions. How such innovations are created and how successful innovation processes can be initiated are therefore extremely important questions. In recent years, it has been recognized that innovations are localized. They are now believed to be the result of ongoing and prolonged collaboration and interaction between firms and a variety of actors around them within what has been termed regional innovation systems. The actors in the regional innovation systems include customers, producers, subcontractors, consultants, governmental institutions, research institutes, universities, etc. Most of the research on regional innovation systems has focused on high-tech clusters in large metropolitan regions well equipped with a broad spectrum of all kinds of actors that are strategic in the innovation process. Much less interest has been devoted to regional innovation systems in small and medium-sized regions that are less diversified as regards strategic actors in the innovation process. The purpose of the current paper is to provide a critical state-of-the-art review of current research on regional innovation systems in small and medium-sized regions. In particular, we focus on what should be meant with a regional innovation system in this context and the possibilities to identify regional innovation systems that are typical for different types of industrial clusters and regions. Regional innovation policies in small and medium-sized regions are also discussed.

Andersson, M. & Karlsson, C., 2004. The Role of Accessibility for the Performance of Regional Innovation Systems. , (09), pp.1–27.

Abstract: The link between proximity and innovation has been dwelled upon extensively in the literature. A regional economic milieu characterized by proximity between relevant actors is maintained to be suitable for establishing and maintaining successful regional innovation system. In this paper it is proposed that the relevant link to be studied is rather that between accessibility and innovation. Although accessibility is a key factor in facilitating the processes stressed to be important for innovations, the relationship between accessibility and innovation is surprisingly unexploited. Scrutinization of the relationship between accessibility and innovation is necessary in order to fully comprehend regional innovative capacity. Furthermore, such scrutinization will shed further light in the issue of the importance of knowledge spillovers.

Anselin, L., Varga, A. & Acs, Z., 1997. Local geographical spillovers between university research and high technology innovations. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 42(3), pp.422–448. Available at: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0094119097920325>.

Abstract: This paper re-examines the empirical evidence on the degree of spatial spillover between university research and high technology innovations. The familiar Griliches–Jaffe knowledge production

function is estimated at both the state and the metropolitan statistical areas (MSA) level and extended with more precise measures of spatial spillover. Alternatives based on the gravity potential and covering indices are formulated for Jaffe's "geographical coincidence index" and found to provide strong evidence of local spillovers at the state level. At the MSA level, a distinction is made between research and development activities and university research in the MSA and in the surrounding counties. Evidence is found of local spatial externalities between university research and high technology innovative activity, both directly and indirectly via private research and development.

Arbia, G., Battisti, M. & Di Vaio, G., 2010. Institutions and geography: Empirical test of spatial growth models for European regions. *Economic Modelling*, 27(1), pp.12–21. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0264999309001163> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This article provides an empirical assessment of the growth experiences of European regions, during the period 1991–2004, by taking into account the spatial effects due to both institutions and geography. These effects have been modelled by means of specific controls and by using a non-conventional spatial weight matrix. Results favour a model dealing with substantive spatial externalities. Within this framework, the country-specific institutions are strongly and positively related to the regional productivity's growth rate. In addition, the geo-institutional proximity increases the spatial dependence of the regional output per worker and raises the speed of convergence. By contrast, the pure geographical metrics is underperforming, while underestimating the convergence dynamics.

Archibugi, D. & Pianta, M., 1994. Aggregate convergence and sectorial specialization in innovation. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 4(1), pp.17–33.

Abstract: Over the last 20 years OECD countries have converged in terms of their innovations, in parallel to the process of economic convergence and catching up in technology. However, this has not led to a similarity in the sectoral strengths of the majority of countries. Applying a measure of "technological distance" between pairs of countries based on patents, it is shown that nations have increased their technological specialization (i.e. their sectoral differences) over the 1980s. An apparent paradox is pointed out, as countries converge by becoming more different and grow by becoming more specialized.

Arencibia, J. & Ríos, X. eds., 2010. *Desarrollo local: hacia un nuevo protagonismo de las ciudades y regiones*, Caracas: Corporación Andina de Fomento. Available at: <http://publicaciones.caf.com/media/1146/124.pdf>.

Asheim, B. et al., 2007. Constructing knowledge-based regional advantage: implications for regional innovation policy. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 7(2-5), pp.140–155.

Abstract: A focus on constructing regional advantage requires an "unpacking" of what makes territorial agglomerations important for innovation and competitiveness by disclosing and revealing the contingencies, particularities and specificities of the various contexts and environments where knowledge creation, innovation and entrepreneurship take place. In order to achieve more effective regional innovation policy, this paper presents and discusses three dimensions along which such unpacking can take place. These dimensions refer to (1) specific industrial knowledge bases, (2) globally distributed knowledge networks and (3) different territorial competence bases.

Asheim, B., 2007. Differentiated Knowledge Bases and Varieties of Regional Innovation Systems. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 20(3), pp.223–241. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13511610701722846> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This article introduces a theoretical and analytical framework for discussing regional development and regional advantage with reference to a regional innovation system strategy. It uses the differentiated knowledge base approach to transcend the traditional codified–tacit dichotomy of knowledge, and for providing a trans-sectoral understanding of economic activities. Different regional innovation systems are presented and described. The discussion of various types of regional innovation systems is contextualized using a variety of capitalist perspectives. The article concludes by discussing the question if regional innovation systems can exist.

Asheim, B.T., 2001. Localized Learning, Innovation and Regional Clusters. In Å. Mariussen, ed. *Cluster Policies – Cluster Development? (Nordregio 2001:2), Report*. Stockholm, pp. 39–58.

Asheim, B.T. & Coenen, L., 2006. Contextualising Regional Innovation Systems in a Globalising Learning Economy: On Knowledge Bases and Institutional Frameworks. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 31(1), pp.163–173. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10961-005-5028-0>.

Abstract: In order to advance the understanding of which types of regional innovation system represent effective innovation support for what kinds of industry in different regions analyses must be contextualized by reference to the actual knowledge base of various industries as well as to the regional and national institutional framework, which strongly shape the innovation processes of firms. Of special importance is the linkage between the larger institutional frameworks of the national innovation and business systems, and the character of regional innovation systems. In making the arguments about a general correspondence between the macro-institutional characteristics of the economy and the dominant form and character of its regional innovation systems a link is provided to the literature on “varieties of capitalism” and national business systems.

Asheim, B.T. & Coenen, L., 2005. Knowledge bases and regional innovation systems: Comparing Nordic clusters. *Research Policy*, 34(8), pp.1173–1190. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733305001101> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The analysis of the importance of different types of regional innovation systems must take place within a context of the actual knowledge base of various industries in the economy, as the innovation processes of firms are strongly shaped by their specific knowledge base. In this paper, we shall distinguish between two types of knowledge base: analytical and synthetic. These types indicate different mixes of tacit and codified knowledge, codification possibilities and limits, qualifications and skills, required organisations and institutions involved, as well as specific competitive challenges from a globalising economy, which have different implications for different sectors of industry, and, thus, for the kind of innovation support needed. The traditional constellation of industrial clusters surrounded by innovation supporting organisations, constituting a regional innovation system, is nearly always to be found in contexts of industries with a synthetic knowledge base (e.g. engineering-based industries), while the existence of regional innovation systems as an integral part of a cluster will normally be the case of industries based on an analytical knowledge base (e.g. science-based industries, such as IT and bio-tech). In the discussion of different types of regional innovation systems five empirical illustrations from a Nordic comparative project on SMEs and regional innovation systems will be used: the furniture industry in Salling, Denmark; the wireless communication industry in North Jutland, Denmark; the functional food industry in Scania, Sweden; the food industry in Rogaland, Norway and the electronics industry in Horten, Norway. We argue that in terms of innovation policy the regional level often provides a grounded approach embedded in networks of actors acknowledging the importance of the knowledge base of an industry.

Asheim, B.T., Coenen, L. & Henning, M.S., 2003. *Nordic SMEs and Regional Innovation Systems*, Lund, Sweden. Available at: http://nordicinnovation.org/Global/_Publications/Reports/2003/Nordic SMEs and Regional Innovation Systems.pdf.

Asheim, B.T. & Isaksen, A., 1997. Location, agglomeration and innovation: Towards regional innovation systems in Norway? *European Planning Studies*, 5(3), pp.299–330. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09654319708720402> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The theoretical part of the article examines the concept of regional innovation systems against the background of modern theories of innovation. The view of interactive learning as a fundamental aspect of the innovation process provides the ground for an interactive innovation model, which is greatly facilitated by geographical proximity and territorial agglomeration. The empirical part analyzes geographical variations in innovation activity in Norwegian industry, as well as examining more thoroughly innovation performance in two industrial agglomerations in Norway. On the basis of the theoretical clarification and empirical analyses carried out, the article finally discuss how to design a regional innovation policy for three main area types in Norway.

Asheim, B.T. & Isaksen, A., 2002. Regional Innovation Systems: The Integration of Local “Sticky” and Global “Ubiquitous” Knowledge. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 27(1), pp.77–86.

Abstract: The paper examines how firms in three regional clusters in Norway dominated by shipbuilding, mechanical engineering and electronics industry, respectively exploit both place-specific local resources as well as external, world-class knowledge to strengthen their competitiveness. From these case-studies we make four points: (1) Ideal-typical regional innovation systems, i.e., regional clusters “surrounded” by supporting local organisations, is rather uncommon in Norway. (2) External contacts, outside of the local industrial milieu, are crucial in innovation processes also in many SMEs. (3) Innovation processes may nevertheless be regarded as regional phenomena in regional clusters, as regional resources and collaborative networks often have decisive significance for firms’ innovation activity. (4) Regional resources include in particular place-specific, contextual knowledge of both tacit and codified nature, that, in combination, is rather geographically immobile.

Audretsch, D.B. & Feldman, M.P., 1996. R&D Spillovers and the Geography of Innovation and Production. *The American Economic Review*, 86(3), pp.630–640.

Autant-Bernard, C., Fadaïro, M. & Massard, N., 2013. Knowledge diffusion and innovation policies within the European regions: Challenges based on recent empirical evidence. *Research Policy*, 42(1), pp.196–210. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733312001692> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This article builds upon the empirical results concerning localised knowledge spillovers in order to highlight some policy implications within the European regions. The analysis emphasises the role of the regional innovation policies as supporting the institutions which generate knowledge and learning. However, it appears that the search for universal policy tools is unrealistic. The empirical literature stresses indeed a variety of regional features. In this perspective, we argue that original strategies have to be built in order to cope with the various dilemmas faced by regional innovation policies, concerning in particular the best way to enhance and exploit public/private, intra/inter-firms, intra/inter-industries and local/global knowledge flows. Such specific strategies require having an accurate knowledge on the local features and on the comparative positioning of the concerned region compared to others. Improving data and indicators to diagnose and monitor regional innovation is therefore presented as a key issue for the policy makers.

Balassa, B., 1965. Trade Liberalisation and “Revealed” Comparative Advantage. *The Manchester School*, 33, pp.99–123.

Barca, F., Mccann, P. & Rodríguez-Pose, A., 2011. The case for regional development intervention: place-based versus place-neutral approaches. , (September), pp.1–36.

Abstract: The paper examines the debates regarding place-neutral versus place-based policies for economic development. The analysis is set in the context of how development policy thinking on the part of both scholars and international organizations has evolved over several decades. Many of the previously accepted arguments have been called into question by the impacts of globalization and a new response to these issues has emerged, a response both to these global changes and also to non-spatial development approaches. The debates are highlighted in the context of a series of major reports recently published on the topic. The cases of the developing world and of the European Union are used as examples of how in this changing context development intervention should increasingly focus on efficiency and social inclusion at the expense of an emphasis on territorial convergence and how strategies should consider economic, social, political and institutional diversity in order to maximize both the local and the aggregate potential for economic development.

Le Bas, C. & Sierra, C., 2002. "Location versus home country advantages" in R&D activities: some further results on multinationals' locational strategies. *Research Policy*, 31(4), pp.589–609.

Abstract: In this paper we study the question of the determinants of the foreign location of technological activities of multinational firms (MNFs): do they locate their knowledge activities as a consequence of their home country advantages or according to host country strengths? We have defined four types of strategy (learning) according to revealed technological advantages. Our results, based on the 345 MNFs with the greatest patenting activity in Europe, globally confirm the main findings of Patel and Vega [Research Policy 28 (2/3) (1999) 145–155]: in a great majority of cases (nearly 70%) MNFs locate their activities abroad in technological areas or fields where they are strong at home (strategies 2 and 3). Moreover, strategy 3, which corresponds with "dynamic learning", outclasses strategy 2, which corresponds with "myopic learning", and becomes increasingly important over time. The strategy of Japanese firms is very different from European and US MNFs: in Europe, Japanese firms seek out locations that have complementary strengths to their own (strategy 2). In terms of policy implications it can be noted that the national system of innovation (in particular the system of academic research) should strengthen the technological advantages of local firms and enable them to successfully locate a part of their R&D activities abroad.

Basile, R. & Girardi, A., 2009. Specialization and risk sharing in European regions. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 10(5), pp.645–659. Available at:
<http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/lbp047> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: Economic theory emphasizes that risk sharing makes it possible to exploit benefits from comparative advantages and economies of scale. Unlike previous studies we test (and reject) the assumption of parameter homogeneity across geographical units in measuring risk sharing. The estimated regional-specific index of risk sharing is then used as a covariate in a model of industrial specialization for the EU15 regions. By estimating a number of nonparametric additive spatial autocovariance models, allowing for nonlinearities and spatial dependence, we show that industrial specialization is positively affected by risk-sharing measures even controlling for other relevant regressors.

Belussi, F., Sammarra, A. & Sedita, S.R., 2010. Learning at the boundaries in an "Open Regional Innovation System": A focus on firms' innovation strategies in the Emilia Romagna life science industry. *Research Policy*, 39(6), pp.710–721. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733310000284> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The paper investigates the existence of an Open Regional Innovation System (ORIS model). This model is characterised by the firms' adoption of an open innovation strategy, which overcomes not only the boundaries of the firms but also the boundaries of the region. Using data collected in a sample of life science firms, our research provides the evidence that the Emilia Romagna RIS has evolved towards an ORIS model, where firms' innovation search strategy, despite being still embedded in local

nets (involving several regional public research organisations – PROs), is open to external-to-the-region research networks and knowledge sources. It also shows that innovation openness influences significantly the firms' innovative performance.

Benedictis, L., Gallegati, M. & Tamberi, M., 2009. Overall trade specialization and economic development: countries diversify. *Review of World Economics*, 145(1), pp.37–55. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10290-009-0007-4> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper provides evidence for an aspect of trade often disregarded in international trade research: countries' sectoral export diversification. The results of our semiparametric empirical analysis show that, on average, countries do not specialize; on the contrary, they diversify. Our results are robust for different statistical indices used to measure trade specialization, for the level of sectoral aggregation, and for the level of smoothing in the nonparametric term associated with per capita income. Using a generalized additive model (GAM) with country-specific fixed effects it can be shown that, controlling for countries' heterogeneity, sectoral export diversification increases with income.

Bergek, A. et al., 2008. Analyzing the functional dynamics of technological innovation systems: A scheme of analysis. *Research Policy*, 37(3), pp.407–429. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S004873330700248X> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Various researchers and policy analysts have made empirical studies of innovation systems in order to understand their current structure and trace their dynamics. However, policy makers often experience difficulties in extracting practical guidelines from studies of this kind. In this paper, we operationalize our previous work on a functional approach to analyzing innovation system dynamics into a practical scheme of analysis for policy makers. The scheme is based on previous literature and our own experience in developing and applying functional thinking. It can be used by policy makers not only to identify the key policy issues but also to set policy goals.

Beugelsdijk, S., McCann, P. & Mudambi, R., 2010. Introduction: Place, space and organization- economic geography and the multinational enterprise. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 10(4), pp.485–493. Available at: <http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/lbq018> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This article discusses the current links between international trade theory, economic geography and strategy and international business. We offer a way forward for building further links between these literatures that focusses on the notions of place, space and organization, and we document how the papers in this special issue contribute to this debate.

Blanc, G. Le, 2000. Regional Specialization, Local Externalities and Clustering in Information Technology Industries. In *40th ERSA Congress (European Regional Science Association). Barcelona, August 29 - September 1, 2000*. Barcelona, Spain: European Regional Science Association, pp. 1–23.

Abstract: Is there a “new” economic geography of Information Technologies driven industries? Does the fast growth of the Digital Economy shape new regional specialization and industrial concentration? How do the different theories of agglomeration externalities contribute to the understanding of clustering dynamics in IT industries? This paper uses geographical data from 1992 and 1997 Census to examine spatial and regional growth patterns of the Digital Economy in the United States. We argue that the regional co-location of the distinct industries (telecoms, software, Internet services, media) making the Information economy, but not their separate regional specialization, encourage employment growth. This “convergence” process helps explaining the emergence of new IT-specialized clusters, amid the traditional high tech States. It also gives some economic substance to the common place idea of IT convergence, which is often solely considered under the technological or business dimension, and presents it as a particular case of Jacobs' dynamic diversity externalities.

Blazek, J. et al., 2013. Emerging regional innovation strategies in Central Europe: institutions and regional leadership in generating strategic outcomes. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 20(2), pp.1–20. Available at: <http://eur.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0969776411428651> [Accessed December 11, 2013].

Abstract: The paper seeks to develop a comparative analysis of approaches to innovation support in three self-governing regions of the Czech Republic. Its analytical section presents an in-depth analysis of the development of innovation policies in three regions: the capital city of Prague, South Moravia and the old industrial region of Moravia-Silesia. Key dimensions of regional innovation strategy in each of the three regions are closely scrutinized and critically examined, within the context of state-of-the-art European approaches to innovation policy. Profound differences, both in approaches to innovation policy design and in the results so far achieved, have been found between the studied regions, reflecting differences in both structural and soft factors in the regions in question. Rapid progress, in terms of innovation strategy implementation, is evident in a region where strong knowledge creation capacity (in both the academic and the business spheres) exists in harmony with professional and enthusiastic key personnel in intermediary institutions as well as steady political support from regional decision-makers. The authors believe that some of their observations will have relevance for innovation policy design and implementation in other Czech regions and in other regions of the European Union's new member states.

Boldrin, M. & Canova, F., 2001. Inequality and convergence in Europe's regions: reconsidering European regional policies. *Economic Policy*, 16(32), pp.205–253. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/1468-0327.00074> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: In this paper we take a critical look at current European regional policies. First, we document the motivation for such policies, that is, the large income disparities across the regions of the EU15. Large disparities are certainly present. Second, we illustrate the various instruments adopted and discuss their underpinnings in established economic theories. Next, we look at available data, searching for three kinds of evidence: (1) if disparities are either growing or decreasing, we conclude they are neither; (2) which are the major factors explaining such disparities and, in particular, if they are the factors predicted by the economic models adopted by the Commission to justify current policies, we conclude this is most certainly not the case; (3) if there are clear signs that EU policies, as opposed to other social and economic factors, are actually reducing such disparities, we cannot find any clear sign of such desired impact. Our conclusion is that regional and structural policies serve mostly a redistributive purpose, motivated by the nature of the political equilibria upon which the European Union is built. They have little relationship with fostering economic growth. This casts a serious doubt on their social value and, furthermore, strongly questions extending such policies to future members of the European Union. A successful EU enlargement, in our view, calls for an immediate and drastic revision of regional economic policies.

Bonaccorsi, A., 2009. Linking industrial competitiveness, R&D specialisation and the dynamics of knowledge in science: a look at remote influences. In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 45–52. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Boons, F. et al., 2013. Sustainable innovation, business models and economic performance: an overview. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 45, pp.1–8. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0959652612004209> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Sustainable development requires radical and systemic innovations. Such innovations can be more effectively created and studied when building on the concept of business models. This concept provides firms with a holistic framework to envision and implement sustainable innovations. For researchers, the concept provides an analytical tool that allows them to assess the interplay between

the different aspects that firms combine to create ecological, economic, and social value. In addition, the business model concept provides a link between the individual firm and the larger production and consumption system in which it operates. This paper provides an introduction to the special issue, which emerged from selected papers presented at the ERSCP-EMSU 2010 Conference held in Delft, The Netherlands. Papers in the special issue cover a broad range, from a conceptual discussion resulting in a research agenda, the assessment of diffusion of specific business models such as Product-Service Systems, the introduction of new management tools for business transition management, to case studies on how specific business models evolved in specific communities. Together, these papers provide insight into the promise of the business model concept for understanding and advancing sustainable innovation.

Boschma, R., 2005. Proximity and innovation: a critical assessment. *Regional Studies*, 39, pp.61–74.

Abstract: A key issue in economic geography is to determine the impact of geographical proximity on interactive learning and innovation. We argue that the importance of geographical proximity cannot be assessed in isolation, but should always be examined in relation to other dimensions of proximity that may provide alternative solutions to the problem of coordination. We claim that geographical proximity per se is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for learning to take place. Nevertheless, it facilitates interactive learning, most likely by strengthening the other dimensions of proximity. However, proximity may also have negative impacts on innovation due to the problem of lock-in. Accordingly, not only too little, but also too much proximity may be detrimental to interactive learning and innovation. This may be the case for all five dimensions of proximity discussed in the paper, i.e. cognitive, organizational, social, institutional and geographical proximity. Finally, the paper presents a number of mechanisms that offer, by their own, or in combination, solutions to the problems of coordination and lock-in. That is, they enhance effective coordination and control (solving the problem of too little proximity), while they prevent actors to become locked-in through ensuring openness and flexibility (solving the problem of too much proximity).

Brookfield, J., 2007. Firm Clustering and Specialization: A Study of Taiwan's Machine Tool Industry. *Small Business Economics*, 30(4), pp.405–422. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11187-007-9047-0> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This study investigates links between firm clustering and firm specialization. The paper argues that firms located in multi-centered, locally owned industrial districts are likely to be relatively specialized. Based on data from 163 companies in Taiwan's machine tool industry, this study finds support for a positive association between location in a multi-centered, locally owned industrial district and firm specialization.

Brühlhart, M., 1996. Regional integration, scale economies and industry location in the European Union. Available at: <http://www.cepr.org/pubs/dps/DP1435.asp>.

Abstract: This paper analyses the effects of regional integration on the location of increasing-returns industry and the resulting pattern of trade. Theoretically, it is shown that regional integration may initially lead to a dispersion of industry inside the customs union. Below a certain threshold of internal trade costs, however, industry concentration in the central member country will again increase. This non-monotonic relationship with regional integration also applies to equilibrium levels of intra-industry trade (IIT). A strictly monotonic negative relationship is found between, on one hand, the degree of scale economies and, on the other hand, industrial concentration both in the central country and intra-union IIT. Empirical evidence for the European Union lends support to some of the theoretical predictions. Employment in scale-intensive industries tends to be concentrated at the centre of the EU, and IIT is relatively low in these sectors. An IIT growth reversal is detected for the scale-intensive industries, which supports the non-monotonicity predicted by the model.

Burger, M.J., van der Knaap, B. & Wall, R.S., 2012. Revealed competition for greenfield investments between European regions. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 13(4), pp.619–648. Available at: <http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/lbs024> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: In the modern economy, cities are assumed to be in fierce competition over attracting foreign investments in leading sectors of the world economy. Despite the rich theoretical discourse on these “wars”, it remains unclear which territories are competing with each other over which types of investments. Combining insights from international economics, international business, and urban systems literature, we develop an indicator to measure revealed competition between territories for investments based on the overlap of investment portfolios of regions. Taking competition for greenfield investments between European regions as a test subject, we identify competitive market segments, derive the competitive threat a region faces from other regions, the competitive threat regions pose to other regions, and the most important market segments in which regions compete. We show that European regions with similar locational endowments pose a fiercer competitive threat to one another. In addition, regions that are sufficiently large and distinctive, face the smallest average competitive threat from all other regions.

Cadarso Vecina, M.Á., López Santiago, L.A. & Tobarra Gómez, M.Á., 2007. Especialización vertical, outsourcing e inversión directa en la industria española = Vertical Specialization Outsourcing and Direct Investment in the Spanish Manufacturing Sector. *Revista de Economía Mundial*, 16, pp.27–55.

Abstract: It is not possible to understand the globalisation process without studying the growing expansion of international trade in intermediate goods. The outsourcing measures used in this paper are calculated from input-output tables and allow us to explain the evolution of intra –and inter– industrial trade for the Spanish manufactures in 1995–2000. Vertical specialization goes a step further by linking imports of inputs required by a country and its exports. Furthermore, this paper analyses the impact on outsourcing of both the presence of multinational firms (MNEs) and the inward and outward flows of direct investment. Our results indicate that in high-tech sectors, the presence of MNEs is linked to high intra-industrial outsourcing, and in some traditional (low-tech) outsourcing is related to Spanish outward FDI.

Camagni, R. & Capello, R., 2013. Regional Innovation Patterns and the EU Regional Policy Reform : Toward Smart Innovation Policies. *Growth and Change*, 44(2), pp.355–389.

Abstract: The present debate on regional policy design to fit the Europe 2020 Agenda calls for additional reflections on the way sectoral policies, like innovation policies, can be translated appropriately into a regional setting. The paper enters the debate on smart specialization strategies by stressing the need to overcome the simplistic dichotomy between core and periphery in the Union and between an advanced “research area” (the core) and a “co-application area” of general purpose technologies to local technological specificities (the periphery). The geography of innovation is much more complex than a simple core-periphery model, and the logical pathway toward innovation is much more complex than the linear model of research and development-invention-innovation direct link: the innovation patterns are differentiated among regions according to their regional context conditions. The identification of specific “innovation patterns” is necessary to design “smart innovation” policies. The paper presents a critique to the smart specialization debate, suggests a new taxonomy of European innovative regions based on their innovation patterns, and proposes innovation policies for each regional mode of innovation.

Canning, D., 1996. Specialization, scale economies and economic development. *Economics Letters*, 52(1), pp.95–100. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0165176596008361>.

Abstract: Manufacturing plants tend to be bigger in large countries, but smaller in countries with high income per capita or strong financial markets. Specialization, with small plants linked through markets or industrial groups, may be a more important source of economic development than scale economies in large plants.

Cantner, U. & Graf, H., 2004. Cooperation and specialization in German technology regions. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 14(5), pp.543–562. Available at:
<http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00191-004-0229-5> [Accessed December 16, 2013].

Abstract: In this paper we focus on the technological knowledge of a region and the pattern of cooperative behavior of the innovative actors within that region as a means of transferring this knowledge. In particular, we are concerned with the relationship between the kind and level of knowledge and/or the degree of specialization within a region, the propensity to cooperate and the kind of cooperation. Based on a theoretical discussion of research cooperation we derive appropriate hypotheses and provide an econometric analysis based on data of co-patenting. We find that technologically moderately specialized regions show the highest number of research cooperations, and the higher a regions specialization, the more cooperations take place with partners inside that region.

Cantwell, J. & Iammarino, S., 2001. EU regions and multinational corporations: change, stability and strengthening of technological comparative advantages. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 10(4), pp.1007–1037.

Abstract: In a rapidly globalizing economy, and particularly in the face of a process of economic integration such as that occurring in the EU, regions forge an increasing number of linkages with other locations within and across national boundaries through the local technological development efforts of multinational corporations (MNCs). By using a database of patents granted to the largest firms by the US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO), we have shown in previous research that the pattern of MNC networks for innovation conforms to an internal (within national boundaries) hierarchy of regional centres. In this paper the hypothesis of the combined significance of cumulateness and incremental change in innovation is examined by testing the extent of continuity in the sectoral composition of technological profiles of different EU regional centres between the 1970s and the 1990s. The results provide support for our hypothesis that a geographical hierarchy of regional locations can be established also across national boundaries within the EU. It is shown that the core European regions can be divided into two kinds—those in which MNCs have consolidated areas of traditional specialisation for the regions in question, and those in which there has been a shift towards (and a relative growth of) the development of fields of high technological opportunities.

Carlsson, B. et al., 2002. Innovation systems: analytical and methodological issues. *Research Policy*, 31(2), pp.233–245.

Abstract: Innovation systems can be defined in a variety of ways: they can be national, regional, sectoral, or technological. They all involve the creation, diffusion, and use of knowledge. Systems consist of components, relationships among these, and their characteristics or attributes. The focus of this paper is on the analytical and methodological issues arising from various system concepts. There are three issues that stand out as problematic. First, what is the appropriate level of analysis for the purpose at hand? It matters, for example, whether we are interested in a certain technology, product, set of related products, a competence bloc, a particular cluster of activities or firms, or the science and technology base generally—and for what geographic area, as well as for what time period. The choice of components and system boundaries depends on this, as does the type of interaction among components to be analyzed. The attributes or features of the system components that come into focus also depend on the choice of level of analysis. The second and closely related issue is how to determine the population, i.e. delineate the system and identify the actors and/or components. What are the key relationships that need to be captured so that the important interaction takes place within the system

rather than outside? The third issue is how to measure the performance of the system. What is to be measured, and how can performance be measured at the system level rather than at component level?

Čenys, A., 2009. R&D specialization and the Lisbon strategy. In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 55–62. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Chang, C.-L., Khamkaew, T. & McAleer, M., 2012. IV estimation of a panel threshold model of tourism specialization and economic development. *Tourism Economics*, 18(1), pp.5–41. Available at: <http://openurl.ingenta.com/content/xref?genre=article&issn=1354-8166&volume=18&issue=1&spage=5> [Accessed January 20, 2014].

Abstract: The significant impact of international tourism in stimulating economic growth is especially important from a policy perspective. For this reason, the relationship between international tourism and economic growth would seem to be an interesting and topical empirical issue. The paper investigates whether tourism specialization is important for economic development in 159 countries over the period 1989–2008. The results from panel threshold regressions show a positive relationship between economic growth and tourism. Instrumental variable estimation of a threshold regression is used to quantify the contributions of tourism specialization to economic growth, while correcting for endogeneity between the regressors and error term. The significant impact of tourism specialization on economic growth in most regressions is robust to different specifications of tourism specialization, as well as to differences in real GDP measurement. However, the coefficients of the tourism specialization variables in the two regimes are significantly different, with a higher impact of tourism on economic growth found in the low regime. These findings do not change with changes in the threshold variables. The empirical results suggest that tourism growth does not always lead to substantial economic growth.

Chapman, S.A. & Meliciani, V., 2012. Income Disparities in the Enlarged EU: Socio-Economic, Specialisation and Geographical Clusters. *Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie*, 103(3), pp.293–311. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1467-9663.2011.00683.x> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: The paper contains a non-parametric analysis of regional convergence in the enlarged EU over the period 1998–2005. It finds overall convergence but growing within country disparities, especially due to the behaviour of newcomer regions. It also finds strong (but falling) spatial correlation of per-capita income. Starting from this evidence, the paper considers the role of socio-economic features, specialisation patterns and geographical factors in explaining within countries disparities. Overall we find that partly specialisation but more evidently socio-economic clusters have a good explanatory power while simple geographical factors do not explain within countries divergence. This does not mean that spatial factors are not important: rather it means that agglomeration alone cannot explain a complex and variegated pattern of growth where structural and socio-economic factors appear to be playing an important and increasing role.

Charles, D., Gross, F. & Bachtler, J., 2012. “Smart Specialisation” and Cohesion Policy – A Strategy for All Regions? IQ-Net Thematic Paper No. 30 (2). In *32nd IQ-Net Conference (Phase V). Tampere, Finland, 18-20 June 2012*. Tampere, Finland: European Policies Research Centre, pp. 1–51.

Chen, K. & Kenney, M., 2007. Universities/Research Institutes and Regional Innovation Systems: The Cases of Beijing and Shenzhen. *World Development*, 35(6), pp.1056–1074. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305750X07000459> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper explores the role of universities and research institutes (URIs) in the development of the Chinese economy through a comparison of the development of the Beijing and Shenzhen technology clusters. The two locations, while embedded in the same national innovation system, have

exhibited completely different evolutionary trajectories. In the case of Beijing, the URIs have played an extremely important role in the development of largest high technology cluster in China. In contrast, in Shenzhen, which is now the third most important cluster in China, has in the last twenty years policy makers have consciously worked to establish and attract institutions of higher education. We suggest that the Chinese experience, though not without problems, provides an interesting model for other nations with strong URIs.

Chou, T.-C., 1985. The pattern and strategy of industrialization in Taiwan - Specialization and offsetting policy. *The Developing Economies*, 23(2), pp.138–157.

Ciccone, A., 2002. Agglomeration effects in Europe. *European Economic Review*, 46(2), pp.213–227.

Abstract: The paper estimates agglomeration-effects for France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the UK. Estimation takes into account endogeneity of the spatial distribution of employment and spatial fixed-effects. Empirical results suggest that agglomeration-effects in these European countries are only slightly smaller than agglomeration-effects in the US: the estimated elasticity of average-labor-productivity with respect to employment-density is 4.5 percent compared to 5 percent in the US.

Combes, P.P. & Overman, H.G., 2004. The spatial distribution of economic activities in the European Union. In J. V. Henderson & J.-F. Thisse, eds. *Handbook of Regional and Urban Economics*. Elsevier, pp. 2845–2909. Available at: <http://www.econ.brown.edu/faculty/henderson/PPCHGO.pdf>.

Abstract: This paper considers the spatial distribution of economic activities in the European Union. It has three main aims. (i) To describe the data that is available in the EU and give some idea of the rich spatial data sets that are fast becoming available at the national level. (ii) To present descriptive evidence on the location of aggregate activity and particular industries and to consider how these location patterns are changing over time. (iii) To consider the nature of the agglomeration and dispersion forces that determine these patterns and to contrast them to forces acting elsewhere, particularly in the U.S. Our survey suggests that much has been achieved in the wave of empirical work that has occurred in the past decade, but that much work remains to be done.

Cooke, P., 2001. Regional Innovation Systems, Clusters, and the Knowledge Economy. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 10(4), pp.945–974. Available at: <http://icc.oupjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/icc/10.4.945> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: This paper presents a systematic account of the idea and content of regional innovation systems following discoveries made by regional scientists, economic geographers and innovation analysts. It considers the conditions and criteria for empirical recognition and judgement as to whether scientifically analysed, concrete cases of innovation activity warrant the designation of regional innovation system. The paper concludes by claiming that the source for Europe's innovation gap with the United States rests on excess reliance on public intervention, which signifies major market failure. The future will require widespread evolution of public innovation support systems along with stronger institutional and organizational support from the private sector.

Cooke, P., 1992. Regional innovation systems: Competitive regulation in the new Europe. *Geoforum*, 23(3), pp.365–382. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0016718592900489>.

Abstract: This paper is concerned with the concept of regulation. Formerly, economic regulation was seen as a necessary corrective to capitalism's cyclical and spatially variable tendencies, enabling a competitive system of economic activity to remain in place without collapsing under the strains of its own internal centrifugal forces. Increasingly, the role of regulation has been reinterpreted, being viewed either as a major source of unnecessary restraint upon enterprise or as a necessary element in enabling firms to compete more effectively. This paper examines the role regulation can play as a form of

proactive support for industry. It does so in three key sections. The first focusses upon three different approaches to regional innovation, drawing on material evidence from Japan, Germany and France. The second focusses upon regional innovation within the United Kingdom, with particular reference to Wales. The third reports upon developments which have attempted to move the microregulatory structure of Wales towards European best practice within the sphere of regional innovation through a process of “learning through interaction” with more dynamic, institutionally networked regions in Europe. The main conclusions of the paper are that such interactive learning can produce evidence of very rapid institutional reactions, although there is a time lag before the economic performance and dynamism of business is harmonized across regions. Nevertheless, the case of regulatory intervention in the development of a network innovation system in Wales testifies to the importance of a regulatory perspective which is equal to tackling the liberating, as well as the controlling, dimensions of regulatory activity.

Cooke, P., 2005. Regionally asymmetric knowledge capabilities and open innovation: Exploring “Globalisation 2”—A new model of industry organisation. *Research Policy*, 34(8), pp.1128–1149.

Abstract: This paper proposes to review and assess social scientific debate about the origins and nature of innovation in modern society. It focuses on three sub-sets of conceptualisation, critique and commentary that refer specifically to sub-national or regional innovation systems. Research in the latter field has grown enormously in recent years. Moreover, new perspectives from other disciplines than regional science have been promoted. One distinctive view of relevance in that it is focused on the role in innovation of specific “entrepreneurial universities” in relation to industry and government is, of course, the “Triple Helix” approach. This is reviewed and sympathetically critiqued. A second view, less sympathetically critiqued here, is one that itself attacks all so-called “new regionalism” for stressing the importance of institutions, industry embeddedness and the micro-science of regional economic development. Dazzled by “Globalisation 1” and the totalising power of “scale” geographies, this rejection of the worth of spatial analysis at less than the global or national “scalar envelope” is assessed for its potential insights into weaknesses of the regional innovation systems approach but found wanting in both technical accuracy and scholarly competence. Finally, the state of the art in regional innovation systems research is sketched by reference both to recent longitudinal findings and elaborations into specific technological fields, particularly but not only Bioregional Innovation Systems that help move us towards a newer theory of economic geography in the knowledge economy, based on “regional knowledge capabilities.” The analysis conclusively proposes “Globalisation 2”, a “ground-up” knowledge-driven evolution of the earlier “top-down” multilateral trade institution and corporately driven “Globalisation 1.”

Cooke, P., 2009. The knowledge economy, spillovers, proximity, and specialization. In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 29–40. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Cooke, P., Gomez Uranga, M. & Etxebarria, G., 1997. Regional innovation systems: Institutional and organisational dimensions. *Research Policy*, 26(4-5), pp.475–491.

Abstract: The paper explores the case for Regional Systems of Innovation. Acknowledging the major contribution of research on National Innovation Systems, it suggests that for conceptual and methodological reasons, mostly concerning problems of scale and complexity, that approach may be complemented in important ways by a subnational focus. Taking an evolutionary economics standpoint, the paper specifies the concepts of “region,” “innovation” and “system” as the prelude to an extended discussion of the importance of financial capacity, institutionalised learning and productive culture to systemic innovation. Building on the notion of regions as occupying different positions on a continuum referring to processes constituting them and their powers vis-à-vis innovation policy, the paper concludes by advocating strengthening of regional level capacities for promoting both systemic learning and interactive innovation.

Cooke, P., Gómez Uranga, M. & Etxebarria, G., 1998. Regional systems of innovation: an evolutionary perspective. *Environment and Planning A*, 30(9), pp.1563–1584.

Abstract: The authors develop the concept of regional systems of innovation and relate it to preexisting research on national systems of innovation. They argue that work conducted in the “new regional science” field is complementary to systems of innovation approaches. They seek to link new regional work to evolutionary economics, and argue for the development of evolutionary regional science. Common elements of interest to evolutionary innovation research and new regional science are important in understanding processes of agglomeration, trust building, innovation, institutions, and learning in regional systems. The authors develop analytical frameworks for designating regional systems of innovation in terms of distinction between institutions and organisations, hard and soft infrastructures, and the cultural superstructure. They conclude that an evolutionary approach assists understanding of regional potential for developing systemic innovation.

Cooke, P. & Memedovic, O., 2003. Strategies for Regional Innovation Systems: Learning Transfer and Applications. , p.25.

Abstract: The paper explains the concept of regional innovation systems. It argues that global economic foci have raised the profile of regions and regional governance not least because of the rise to prominence of regional and local business clusters as vehicles for global and national economic competitiveness. Key definitions are given and distinctions drawn. The, by reference to a number of important dimensions characterizing innovation such as education, knowledge transfer, linkage and communications, four regions from Asia, Europe and Latin America are contrasted. It is shown that regional innovation systems can be underdeveloped by being too dependent on public support, but equally, and over-emphasis on private infrastructures needs to be guarded against except at the most advanced developmental level. A combination of public and private governance at regional level to promote systemic innovation is advocated.

Cutrini, E., 2010. Specialization and Concentration from a Twofold Geographical Perspective: Evidence from Europe. *Regional Studies*, 44(3), pp.315–336. Available at:
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400802378743> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: Specialization and concentration from a twofold geographical perspective: evidence from Europe, *Regional Studies*. This paper investigates European location patterns during a period of economic integration, seeking to identify the distinct roles played by the different geographical levels. The evolution of localization in Europe proved much more complicated empirically than the predictions based on Krugman’s hypothesis. Using Eurostat regional data for the period 1985–2001, the paper shows that while manufacturing employment trickled down among regions, after the completion of the European Single Market a slight agglomeration occurred, but only across national boundaries. National specialization has emerged particularly in the European Union founding Member States. Moreover, there is evidence of an increasing polarization of the North–South divide closely connected with the growing concentration of high-technology sectors.

D’Allura, G.M., Galvagno, M. & Li Destri, A.M., 2012. Regional Innovation Systems: A Literature Review. *Business Systems Review*, 1(1), pp.139–156.

Abstract: Though various authors have offered reviews of the Regional Innovation Systems (RIS) literature and some have described their personal intellectual voyage amongst the building blocks that constitute this area of scientific enquiry (for example, Cooke 2008), these often illuminating illustrations are nonetheless subjective and, thus, suffer from biases which pertain to the actor performing the analysis. The study proposed in this paper aims to overcome the aforementioned limitation by elaborating an objective review of the main contributions to the RIS field of research, highlighting the

main themes studied and the principal approaches followed. The analysis has been conducted following the Author Co-citation method, applied to the literature regarding RIS present in the Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) of Thomson-ISI in the time span from 1990 to 2009. The results allow to trace an overview of how the RIS research area is actually composed, identifying six main research themes which characterize the field and varied approaches according to which each theme has been analyzed. Main contributions are positioned against each other in order to foster an increase in efforts from future research.

D'Costa, A.P., 2011. Geography, uneven development and distributive justice: the political economy of IT growth in India. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 4(2), pp.237–251.
Available at: <http://cjres.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/cjres/rsr003> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The aim of the paper is to apply a political economy framework both to explain the rise of the information technology (IT) industry and to analyse the spatial and developmental consequences of this growth, especially the distributive dimension on the wider society. The purpose is also to reveal the contradictions associated with the industry, question the crude optimism surrounding the IT sector's transformative capabilities, and by extension, assess the "model" of development implicit with its growth trajectory. As there is class bias in the workings of the sector, which excludes large swathes of the population and reproduces educational inequality, policy implications are briefly discussed.

Dall'erba, S. & Le Gallo, J., 2008. Regional convergence and the impact of European structural funds over 1989–1999: A spatial econometric analysis. *Papers in Regional Science*, 87(2), pp.219–244.
Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1435-5957.2008.00184.x> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper evaluates the impact of structural funds on the convergence process between 145 European regions over 1989–1999. The presence of spillover effects is investigated with spatial econometric methods, which assess the impact of the funds on the targeted region and its neighbours. We also control the potential endogeneity problem in the estimation of their impact. Our estimation results indicate that significant convergence takes place, but that the funds have no impact on it. Simulation experiments show how investments targeted to the peripheral regions never spill over to their neighbours, which calls for a reconsideration of current regional policy tools.

Dalum, B., Laursen, K. & Verspagen, B., 1999. Does specialization matter for growth? *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 8(2), pp.267–288.

Abstract: The question concerning the extent to which the growth performance of an economy is determined by its external relations is a controversial one. There are several approaches which stress the interaction between international factors and domestic growth performance. In the Keynesian tradition, Kaldor and Thirlwall have argued that exports and trade performance are the main determinants of growth. This paper takes different elements from these and other theoretical approaches, and combines them into a framework that stresses the importance of specialization for economic growth. The paper applies a data set on growth and trade in 11 manufacturing sectors, for the period 1965–1988, for the OECD area. The main novelty in the database is the assignment of 75 products in the trade data to the 11 industrial sectors. The relationship between growth and specialization has been tested by running a regression with the sectoral growth of value added as the dependent variable, and several variables, including some measuring specialization as well as other factors, as the independent variables. The regression results presented seem to indicate that specialization does indeed matter for economic growth. However, this impact seems to be gradually wearing off during the 1980s, as is the case for other factors included in the regression analysis.

David, P., Foray, D. & Hall, B., 2013. *Measuring Smart Specialisation: The concept and the need for indicators*,

Davis, D. & Weinstein, D., 1999. Economic geography and regional production structure: an empirical investigation. *European Economic Review*, 43, pp.379–407.

Abstract: There are two principal theories of why countries or regions trade: comparative advantage and increasing returns to scale. Yet there is virtually no empirical work that assesses the relative importance of these two theories in accounting for production structure and trade. We use a framework that nests an increasing returns model of economic geography featuring “home market effects” with that of Heckscher-Ohlin. We employ these trade models to account for the structure of regional production in Japan. We find support for the existence of economic geography effects in eight of nineteen manufacturing sectors, including such important ones as transportation equipment, iron and steel, electrical machinery, and chemicals. Moreover, we find that these effects are economically very significant. The latter contrasts with the results of Davis and Weinstein (1996), which found scant economic significance of economic geography for the structure of OECD production. We conclude that while economic geography may explain little about the international structure of production, it is very important for understanding the regional structure of production.

Deas, I. & Ward, K.G., 2000. From the “new localism” to the “new regionalism”? The implications of regional development agencies for city–regional relations. *Political Geography*, 19(3), pp.273–292. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0962629899000852>.

Abstract: Throughout the last three decades efforts to regenerate British cities have been based around the construction of new institutional alliances and policy networks supported by a series of urban-based initiatives. Successive Conservative governments premised their intervention on the assumption that cities (and particular parts therein) were the most appropriate geographical level around which to organise policy intervention. In pursuing this city-based agenda, the policies were themselves instrumental in constituting the city as an object of policy: a problem in need of a solution. The aim of this paper, however, is not to explore how certain spaces or scales become constructed through, for example, government policy, political practices or state restructuring. Rather the paper augments work conducted on the socially constructed nature of “cities” and “regions”. It explores for regeneration policy and politics the implications of the tendential shift away from a model of “new localism” towards an alternative model of “new regionalism”. The origins of the central element of New Labour’s emergent regional project — the Regional Development Agencies (RDAs) — are established before the paper moves on to examine the likely political relationships between the local state, drawing upon the example of Manchester, and the regional state, drawing upon North West England, under the new institutional arrangements.

Dewhurst, J.H.L. & McCann, P., 2002. A Comparison of Measures of Industrial Specialization For Travel-to-work Areas in Great Britain, 1981-1997. *Regional Studies*, 36(5), pp.541–551. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400220137146> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: That industrial specialization is inversely correlated with regional size is an established empirical finding. However in establishing this relationship, authors have used several different measures of regional industrial specialization or diversification. This review paper investigates whether the choice of measure is important in such work. Eleven different measures found in the literature are compared with respect to their distributions, their degree of correspondence and their behaviour over time. It is found that there appear, within this set, to be three groups of measures. Within each group results are relatively consistent, whereas between each group the differences are quite marked. This suggests that results might be influenced by the choice of specialization measure used.

Dodgson, M. et al., 2008. The evolving nature of Taiwan's national innovation system: The case of biotechnology innovation networks. *Research Policy*, 37(3), pp.430–445. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733307002491> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The dynamics of national innovation systems (NISs) are a source of considerable academic and policy interest, especially when to address new competitive challenges they involve changing institutions and relationships within successful systems. This paper examines the case of Taiwan which is embarking on a new phase in its approach to building its national innovative capacity through creating the infrastructure for a biotechnology industry. By examining the process and mechanisms by which new biotechnology innovation networks are being created, and contrasting their development with existing networks, we analyse the dynamics of Taiwan's NIS. The paper reviews the prospects for this new phase in Taiwan's transition from "imitation" to "innovation". The paper aims to add to the understanding of how innovation systems evolve. It is concerned with the contributors, processes and challenges of NIS evolution and the form and meaning of its dynamic changes.

Doloreux, D., 2004. Regional Innovation Systems in Canada: A Comparative Study. *Regional Studies*, 38(5), pp.479–492. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0143116042000229267> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The Regional Innovation System (RIS) has become a leading approach in explaining the innovation processes and patterns experienced by firms and industries at the regional level. This paper investigates the innovation activities of small and medium sized enterprises in different regions, assesses the extent of their involvement in systemic innovation with other organizations, and examines the nature of regional and more diffused forms of interaction in innovation activity. The discussion draws its empirical substance from the Ottawa and Beauce regions of Canada, regions characterized by different preconditions to innovation in terms of industrial production structure and institutional environments. The results indicate that the innovation activities of surveyed firms in the two regions converge into a similar pattern, as far as innovation practices, information sources and the role of geography are concerned. In addition, the significance of the region as a support to innovation is not confirmed; firms make use of regional, national and even global knowledge sources to sustain innovation.

Doloreux, D., 2003. Regional Innovation Systems in the periphery: the case of the Beauce in Québec (Canada). *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 07(01), pp.67–94. Available at: <http://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/S1363919603000738> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: All too often, innovation research emphasizes core regions exemplifying successful innovation systems or "learning regions" such as, Silicon Valley, Route 128, Emilia-Romagna and Baden-Württemberg. However, lessons learned from these regions are seldom applicable elsewhere, in particular to territories where actors strategic to the innovation process are less diversified. The regional innovation system (RIS) in peripheral regions, and the likelihood of their acting as conduits for the innovation system, have seldom been the subjects of discussion. The objective of this paper is to study the way in which innovation occurs, including an investigation of actual innovation activities and capabilities of firms located in a peripheral area, and specific factors affecting their innovation activities. The discussion draws its empirical substance from the case of the Beauce in Québec (Canada). A survey of 45 SMEs was conducted in order to get a better understanding of the key dimensions of innovation activities. Read More: <http://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/S1363919603000738>

Doloreux, D., 2002. What we should know about regional systems of innovation. *Technology in Society*, 24(3), pp.243–263. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0160791X02000076>.

Abstract: The concept of Regional Systems of Innovation (RSI) has recently become popular among academics of various disciplines. RSI results from a territorially embedded institutional infrastructure and a production system. The central idea is that the innovative performance of an economy depends on the innovative capabilities of firms and research institutions, and on the ways they interact with each other and public institutions. In this paper, discussion is structured around four key questions: (1) From which theoretical perspectives has the concept of RSI originated?; (2) Does this concept derive from other forms of industrial organization?; (3) Can different forms of RSI exist?; (4) What does the RSI concept fail to address?

Doloreux, D. & Dionne, S., 2008. Is regional innovation system development possible in peripheral regions? Some evidence from the case of La Pocatière, Canada. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 20(3), pp.259–283. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/08985620701795525> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The aim of this paper is to contribute to a greater understanding of the research on innovation systems in peripheral regions by providing a detailed account of the case of the La Pocatière region in Canada. In analysing this case, we raise the following two questions: (1) what are the actors and structure of the innovation system in La Pocatière?; (2) what are the key factors and dynamics leading to innovation activity, as well as to the transformation and growth of this regional innovation system? The empirical bases for the analyses are derived from various sources: historical documents, statistical data, and in-depth interviews with key individuals in private and public organizations.

Doloreux, D., Dionne, S. & Jean, B., 2007. The Evolution of an Innovation System in a Rural Area: The Case of La Pocatière, Québec. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 31(1), pp.146–167. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1468-2427.2007.00707.x> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This article aims to examine the development trajectory of a local innovation system in a rural region, namely La Pocatière, Québec (Canada), from an extended historical perspective (1830–2005). More specifically, its objective is to identify and analyse historical factors that give us a better understanding of the main determinants of the special heritage of this innovation system and of the institutional context in which it emerged and evolved. In short, the relation between the dynamics of innovation and institutional change is examined over time. Historical documents are analysed and the research provides a description and contextualization of the development of this innovation system, and of its spread, particularly in the farming and agricultural-science sector initially, and subsequently in technological and industrial areas (physical technologies and the transport equipment industry). Four main periods are described, corresponding to changes in types of institutional behaviour in relation to innovation: a phase of setting up pioneering institutions and innovations (1827–1911), a phase of growth and influence of the agricultural-science institutions (1911–62), a phase of rupture, economic diversification and development of the technological cluster (1962–97), and a phase of redeployment and growing complexity of the elements of the innovation system (1997–2005).

Doloreux, D. & Parto, S., 2004a. Regional Innovation Systems: A Critical Synthesis. , (August), pp.1–38. Available at: <http://www.intech.unu.edu/publications/discussion-papers/2004-17.pdf>.

Abstract: In recent years, the concept of Regional Innovation Systems has evolved into a widely used analytical framework generating the empirical foundation for innovation policy making. Yet, the approaches utilizing this framework remain ambiguous on such key issues as the territorial dimension of innovation, e.g., the region, and the apparently important role played by “institutions” or the institutional context in the emergence and sustenance of regional innovation systems. This paper reviews and summarizes the most important ideas and arguments of the recent theorizing on regional innovation systems to provide the basis for a critical examination of such issues as (1) definition

confusion and empirical validation; (2) the territorial dimension of regional innovation systems; and (3) the role of institutions. Far from having the last word on these issues, our intent in this paper is to draw attention to the definitional deficiencies of regional system of innovation theorizing and the need to address them.

Doloreux, D. & Parto, S., 2004b. Regional Innovation Systems: Current Discourse and Challenges for Future Research. In *ERSA 2004. Porto, Portugal*. Porto, Portugal: European Regional Science Association, pp. 1–26. Available at: <http://www-sre.wu-wien.ac.at/ersa/ersaconfs/ersa04/PDF/56.pdf>.

Abstract: In recent years, the concept of Regional Innovation Systems has evolved into a widely used analytical framework generating the empirical foundation for innovation policy making. Yet, the approaches utilizing this framework remain ambiguous on such key issues as the territorial dimension of innovation, e.g., the region, and the apparently important role played by “institutions” or the institutional context in the emergence and sustenance of regional innovation systems. This paper reviews and summarizes the most important ideas and arguments of the recent theorizing on regional innovation systems to provide the basis for a critical examination of such issues as (1) definition confusion and empirical validation; (2) the territorial dimension of regional innovation systems; and (3) the role of institutions.

Doloreux, D. & Parto, S., 2005. Regional innovation systems: Current discourse and unresolved issues. *Technology in Society*, 27(2), pp.133–153. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0160791X05000035> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: In recent years, the concept of regional innovation systems has evolved into a widely used analytical framework that generates the empirical foundation for innovation policy making. Yet, the approaches that utilize this framework remain ambiguous on such key issues as the territorial dimension of innovation, i.e. the region, and the apparently important role played by “institutions” or the institutional context in the emergence and sustenance of regional innovation systems. This paper reviews and summarizes important ideas and arguments in the recent theorizing on regional innovation systems. It also examines such issues as (a) definition confusion and empirical validation; (b) the territorial aspect of regional innovation systems; and (c) the role of institutions.

Duranton, G. & Puga, D., 2005. From sectoral to functional urban specialisation. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 57(2), pp.343–370. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0094119004001093> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: Striking evidence is presented of a previously unremarked transformation of urban structure from mainly sectoral to mainly functional specialisation. We offer an explanation showing that this transformation is inextricably interrelated with changes in firms’ organisation. A greater variety of business services for headquarters and of sector-specific intermediates for production plants within a city reduces costs, while congestion increases with city size. A fall in the costs of remote management leads to a transformation of the equilibrium urban and industrial structure. Cities shift from specialising by sector—with integrated headquarters and plants—to specialising mainly by function—with headquarters and business services clustered in larger cities, and plants clustered in smaller cities.

Edgington, D.W., 2008. The Japanese Innovation System: University–Industry Linkages, Small Firms and Regional Technology Clusters. *Prometheus: Critical Studies in Innovation*, 26(1), pp.1–19. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/08109020701846009> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This essay introduces the articles in a special edition on advances made in the Japanese innovation system. It sets the papers against a broad overview of traditional Japanese approaches to

innovation and recent calls for change. An analysis is made of the geography of high-technology factories and recent job losses in the manufacturing sector. The new policies and their impact on Japan's national and regional innovation systems are then outlined and a synopsis given of the other papers in this special edition. The essay makes a number of concluding remarks on the appropriateness of Japan following the US-model of innovation.

Ellison, G. & Glaeser, E., 1999. The geographic concentration of industry: does natural advantage explain agglomeration? *American Economic Review*, 89(2), pp.311–316.

Essletzbichler, J., 2003. From Mass Production to Flexible Specialization: The Sectoral and Geographical Extent of Contract Work in US Manufacturing, 1963 – 1997. *Regional Studies*, 37(8), pp.37–41.

Abstract: Over the last two decades much work in economic geography focused on a fundamental reorganization of capitalist production summarized as shift from Fordist mass production to flexible specialization. Complementing this shift to flexible forms of production is the revival of interest in Marshallian industrial districts characterized by geographically localized and tightly linked networks of small firms. Many a claim was based on anecdotal evidence in selected industries and regions. In order to strengthen the importance of these results, it is necessary to provide comprehensive empirical evidence across a broad range of sectors and regions. This paper traces the key developments in economic geography and examines empirically the extent of flexible specialization in US manufacturing. More specifically the paper focuses on one aspect of this shift and investigates the increase in contract work across all US manufacturing sectors and regions between 1963 and 1997. Employing plant level data for US manufacturing industries, this paper emphasizes the significance of the shift to flexible specialization supported by an increase in the use of contract work across a vast majority of manufacturing sectors, states and metropolitan areas. The paper also demonstrates that pronounced industrial differences prevail and that high contract work ratios explain metropolitan differences in productivity in some but not all sectors.

European Commission, 2009a. *EUR 24049 — Exploring regional structural and S&T specialisation: implications for policy*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/exploring_regional_structural_and_s_t_specialisation.pdf.

European Commission, 2010. *EUR 24198 – International Science & Technology Specialisation: Where does Europe stand?*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/docs/en/4th-regional-key-figure.pdf>.

European Commission, 2009b. *Knowledge for Growth: Prospects for science, technology and innovation: selected papers from Research Commissioner Janez Potočnik's Expert Group*, Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/selected_papers_en.pdf.

Farole, T., Rodríguez-Pose, A. & Storper, M., 2011. Cohesion Policy in the European Union: Growth, Geography, Institutions. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 49(5), pp.1089–1111. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1468-5965.2010.02161.x> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Since the reform of the Structural Funds in 1989, the EU has made the principle of cohesion one of its key policies. Much of the language of European cohesion policy eschews the idea of trade-offs between efficiency and equity, suggesting it is possible to maximize overall growth while also achieving continuous convergence in outcomes and productivity across Europe's regions. Yet, given the rise in inter-regional disparities, it is unclear that cohesion policy has altered the pathway of development from what would have occurred in the absence of intervention. This article draws on geographical economics, institutionalist social science and endogenous growth theory, with the aim of providing a fresh look at cohesion policy. By highlighting a complex set of potential trade-offs and interrelations – overall growth

and efficiency; inter-territorial equity; territorial democracy and governance capacities; and social equity within places – it revisits the rationale of cohesion policy, with particular attention to the geographical dynamics of economic development.

Feldman, M. & Rosenfeld, S., 2011. Southern regional innovation strategies. In D. P. Gitterman & P. A. Coclanis, eds. *A Way Forward: Building a Globally Competitive South*. Global Research Institute, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, pp. 115–119.

Feldman, M.P. & Audretsch, D.B., 1999. Innovation in cities: Science-based diversity, specialization and localized competition. *European Economic Review*, 43(2), pp.409–429.

Abstract: Whether diversity or specialization of economic activity better promotes technological change and subsequent economic growth has been the subject of a heated debate in the economics literature. The purpose of this paper is to consider the effect of the composition of economic activity on innovation. We test whether the specialization of economic activity within a narrow concentrated set of economic activities is more conducive to knowledge spillovers or if diversity, by bringing together complementary activities, better promotes innovation. The evidence provides considerable support for the diversity thesis but little support for the specialization thesis.

Fink, G., 2009. Comparative advantage, regional specialization and income distribution: The case of Austria in perspective. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 31(2), pp.239–259. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0161893808000689> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Realization of comparative advantage (David Ricardo) raises issues of income distribution that emerge when specialization gains are achieved. While the Stolper-Samuelson theorem “predicts” that because of trade liberalization in “rich countries” like Austria or Germany wages may fall and real incomes of capital owners might increase, some doubts are raised whether continuous cuts in relative wages – as a response to specialization gains achieved in the process of trade liberalization – are an adequate policy response. The case of Austria illustrates the related issues. This case is not representative for the EU at large, a similar result can be expected for a few other EU countries, e.g. Germany. Other EU member states pursue different policies.

Fiscato, G., 2007. *Integrated systems for territorial competitiveness: firms, networks, clusters and institutions*. University Institute for Modern Languages, Italy.

Foray, D. et al., 2012. *Guide to research and innovation strategies for smart specialisation (RIS 3)*, Available at: http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/c/document_library/get_file?uuid=e50397e3-f2b1-4086-8608-7b86e69e8553.

Foray, D., 2009. Understanding “smart specialisation.” In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 14–26. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Foray, D. & Ark, B. Van, 2007. Smart specialisation in a truly integrated research area is the key to attracting more R&D to Europe. , (October), p.4.

Abstract: There are concerns expressed at different levels in Europe about the increasing numbers of European companies which are basing their R&D operations outside Europe, at the same time as the number of overseas companies carrying out their R&D in Europe is falling. This phenomenon of the “internationalisation” of R&D does not necessarily have to be negative for Europe, say an influential group of economists, who advise the European Science and Research Commissioner, Janez Potočnik. But they say that if Europe is to benefit from the increasing trend towards R&D being performed internationally, it has to make fundamental changes to the way in which R&D is organised there. The

creation of truly European centres of excellence will be of more benefit in the long run than each individual country having low-level expertise in a full range of scientific areas.

Foray, D., David, P.A. & Hall, B., 2009. Smart Specialisation – The Concept. *Knowledge Economists Policy Brief n° 9*, (June), pp.1–5. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/kfg_policy_brief_no9.pdf.

Abstract: This brief introduces the basic concept of “Smart Specialisation” (SS) which has been a leading idea of the Knowledge for Growth expert group (K4G). The concept is spelled out in more detail in Policy Brief N° 1 in relation to globalisation. Other K4G Policy Briefs that refer to the concept are those on Catching-up Member States (N° 5) and on technology and specialisation (N°8).

Foray, D., David, P.A. & Hall, B.H., 2011. Smart specialization: from academic idea to political instrument, the surprising career of a concept and the difficulties involved in its implementation. , pp.1–16.

Abstract: Smart specialisation is a policy concept that has enjoyed a short but very exciting life! Elaborated by a group of academic “experts” in 2008, it very quickly made a significant impact on the policy audience, particularly in Europe. Such a success story in such a short period of time is a perfect example of “policy running ahead of theory”: while smart specialisation seems to be already a policy hit and policy makers show some frenetic engagements towards smart specialisation, the concept is not tight in particular as an academic concept. Many statements and arguments about smart specialisation have not been yet based on a sound base of empirical work so that the plea in favor of smart specialisation and the tools and instruments to support a smart specialisation strategy are made of more wishes and hopes than of empirical (stylized) facts. There is therefore a growing gap between the policy practice and the theory. In this paper, we expose and explain the minimal set of arguments and statements that have created this situation of smart specialisation having “political salience” which makes policy makers eager to “do it” in spite of a modest theoretical framework to guide its application or an adequate evidence base to help regulate its implementation. Then we will define a research agenda that addresses issues of fundamental understanding, empirical observations and measures and operationalization of the assessment of potential for smart specialisation and of the tools to realize the potential of the concept.

Freeman, C., 2002. Continental , national and sub-national innovation systems — complementarity and economic growth. *Research Policy*, 31(2), pp.191–211.

Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to discuss the relevance of innovation systems to economic growth rates over the last two centuries. The focus is on complementarity (or lack of it) between sub-systems of society and on models of active learning in catching up economies. The paper discusses variations in rates of growth of economic regions and the extent to which variations may be attributed to “innovation systems”. The analysis is applied to Britain in the 18th century, the United States in the second half of the 19th century and the innovation systems of catching up countries in the 20th century.

Giannitsis, A., 2009. Towards an appropriate policy mix for specialisation. In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 63–70. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Giuliani, E., 2007. The selective nature of knowledge networks in clusters: evidence from the wine industry. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 7(2), pp.139–168. Available at: <http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/lbl014> [Accessed January 13, 2014].

Abstract: Most of the studies about industrial clusters and innovation stress the importance of firms’ geographical proximity and their embeddedness in local business networks (BNs) as factors that positively affect their learning and innovation processes. More recently, scholars have started to claim

that firm-specific characteristics should be considered to be central in the process of learning and innovation in clusters. This article contributes to this latter direction of research. It applies social network analysis to explore the structural properties of knowledge networks in three wine clusters in Italy and Chile. The results show that in spite of firms' geographical proximity and the pervasiveness of local BNs, innovation-related knowledge is diffused in clusters in a highly selective and uneven way. This pattern is found to be related to the heterogeneous and asymmetric distribution of firm knowledge bases in the clusters.

Gorg, H. & Ruane, F., 1999. US Investment in EU Member Countries: The Internal Market and Sectoral Specialization. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 37(2), pp.333–348. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/1468-5965.00166> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Griliches, Z., 1992. The search for R&D spillovers. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 94, pp.29–47. Available at: <http://www.nber.org/papers/w3768>.

Abstract: R&D spillovers are, potentially, a major source of endogenous growth in various recent “New Growth Theory” models. This paper reviews the basic model of R&D spillovers and then focuses on the empirical evidence for their existence and magnitude. It reviews the older empirical literature with special attention to the econometric difficulties of actually coming up with convincing evidence on this topic. Taken individually, many of the studies are flawed and subject to a variety of reservations, but the overall impression remains that R&D spillovers are both prevalent and important.

Grillo, F. & Landabaso, M., 2011. Merits, problems and paradoxes of regional innovation policies. *Local Economy*, 26(6-7), pp.544–561. Available at: http://ipts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/activities/research-and-innovation/documents/innovationstrategies_grillo_landabaso.pdf.

Abstract: Public investments in innovation and research assets have been recently perceived by policy makers as an effective tool for the development of less developed regions. This has been particularly true in the case of the European cohesion policies and the structural funds expenditures. However, the expectations have not always been matched by effective results. This article will examine the problem in three main sections. In the first we will review the debate about whether regional imbalances can be corrected by market forces and what is, eventually, the role that regional innovation strategies can play within cohesion programmes. In the second we will discuss the so called “regional innovation paradox” and the problems of designing and implementing strategies within less developed regions. In the third we will identify 10 criteria that programme managers at EU, national and regional levels should consider as they try to solve those problems.

Hajek, P., Henriques, R. & Hajkova, V., 2013. Visualising components of regional innovation systems using self-organizing maps—Evidence from European regions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Published . Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0040162513001650> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Regional innovation systems are regarded as complex systems in which components are strongly dependent on each other. Such relationships can have both linear and nonlinear character. One of the ways to investigate the structure of regional innovation systems is to use a self-organizing map resulting from an unsupervised learning process. In this paper we employed this procedure to visualize and study the patterns present in the individual components of European regional innovation systems. Our findings suggest that there is a similar level of diversity in individual regional innovation systems' components due to their strong intercorrelations. Additionally, the visualisation of the components in geographical maps shows on a positive effect of the Knowledge intensive regions on the spatially close Catching up regions. Finally, the economic growth of the European regions appears to be associated to European economic integration (for lagging behind regions) and the level of innovative and entrepreneurial activity (for knowledge intensive regions).

Hall, L.A. & Bagchi-Sen, S., 2007. An analysis of firm-level innovation strategies in the US biotechnology industry. *Technovation*, 27(1-2), pp.4–14. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0166497206000757> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This study examines factors that may affect innovation strategies and performance of firms in the biotechnology industry. Specifically, differences between factors common to firms with high R&D intensity and those to firms with low R&D intensity are investigated. Biotechnology firms with relatively higher levels of R&D intensity attribute their innovation performance to research-based innovation factors and strategies such as strengthening their own research capabilities, entering into research collaborations with universities, industry leaders and other biotech firms, and licensing their technology. These strategies can be summarized as alignment within the industry. Firms with relatively lower R&D intensity have a hybrid focus—they invest in R&D but may also have products on the market. These firms attribute their innovation performance more so to production-based innovation factors and strategies such as gaining market access and maintaining connections with customers. Their strategy focuses on competitiveness, marketing, and distribution channels, while not ignoring the importance of a strong research base and the need to advance technologically. In a sense, strategies employed to achieve successful innovation reflect the stage of innovation in which a firm is operating for a particular product or process.

Hallet, M., 2000. Regional specialization and concentration in the EU. , p.29. Available at:
http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/publications/publication_summary10532_en.htm.

Abstract: Spatial issues have received renewed interest in economics following the development of the new economic geography. At the same time, there is a general concern that the process of European integration would lead to higher regional specialisation making regions more prone to adverse shocks and increasing adjustment costs in the case of a relocation of firms. However, empirical evidence on spatial patterns of specialisation following the integration of economies is very scarce and inconclusive. Due to problems of data availability, this holds in particular for the regional, sub-national level in Europe. The objective of this paper is to provide some new empirical evidence on these issues on the basis of data for gross value added in 17 sectors and 119 regions between 1980 and 1995. The two main results are that the general process of structural change from manufacturing into services tends to make regions more similar regarding their specialisation and that significant changes in industrial concentration can hardly be identified.

Harrison, M., 2009. Does high-quality research require “critical mass”? In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van (eds. . Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 53–54. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Harvey, C., Green, E.M. & Corfield, P.J., 1999. Continuity, change, and specialization within metropolitan London: the economy of Westminster, 1750-1820. *The Economic History Review*, 52(3), pp.469–493. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/1468-0289.00133> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Helpman, E., 1998. *General purpose technologies and economic growth*, Cambridge, Massachusetts: MIT Press.

Van den Hove, S. et al., 2012. The Innovation Union: a perfect means to confused ends? *Environmental Science & Policy*, 16, pp.73–80. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1462901111001778> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: In this commentary we argue that innovation is a means, not an end in itself. Innovation is only desirable to the extent that it improves human health and well-being and contributes to environmental, social, and economic sustainability. If innovation is merely focussed on bringing more products to markets and delivering economic growth in the short term, as is currently the trend in the European

Union and many OECD countries, it is unclear how it differs from the dominant pre-crisis approach which, notwithstanding its positive effects on living standards, led to unsustainable resource use, crippling biodiversity loss, and increasing greenhouse gas emissions. As the future European research, development and innovation policies are being defined, we should not miss an historic opportunity to concentrate on improving human health, well-being and quality of life, and to embark on a more ecologically, socially and economically sustainable path. Given the scale and irreversibility of our damaging effects on the environment and on the well-being of current and future generations, we call for these aspects to be urgently represented in European innovation discourses, policies, and actions. Re-balancing market focussed innovation and socially meaningful and responsible innovation (i.e. innovation with a human purpose) can be achieved by building on a broader concept of innovation which not only includes technological innovation, but also non-technological, social, institutional, organisational and behavioural innovation. We then discuss the importance of curiosity-driven research and of environment and health research as drivers of socially meaningful innovation in all its forms.

Howells, J., 2005. Innovation and regional economic development: A matter of perspective? *Research Policy*, 34(8), pp.1220–1234. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733305001150> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper investigates the issue of innovation policy within a regional context. It is presented that the perspective one takes is important both in how one interprets the processes and relationships involved, but also in the way one identifies barriers and problems in policy formation and how one resolves them. The paper explores a number of contrasting perspectives in relation to innovation policy and the regions and seeks to highlight the implications of this both for policy, but also in the development of our conceptual understanding about innovation and geography.

Huggins, R., 1997. Regional competitive specialization. Development agency sector initiatives in Wales. *Area*, 29(3), pp.241–252.

Abstract: This paper provides evidence of the movement towards a sector-based approach to regional development by the Welsh Development Agency, its effects on economic competitiveness and its role as a focal point for stimulating the development of specialized industrial clusters. The paper concentrates on the initiatives taking place in the electronics/IT, automotive and healthcare sectors in Wales, and the development of clustering through vertical linkages in the machine tooling sector.

Hunt-McCool, J. & Bishop, D.M., 1998. Health economics and the economics of education: specialization and division of labor. *Economics of Education Review*, 17(3), pp.237–244. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0272775797000459>.

Abstract: This paper addresses the separation of human capital studies into separate fields of education and health. The main difference between the two fields may be the inability to measure the value added of health care expenditures objectively in contrast to earnings valuation of education. As a result, the two fields separate theoretically and methodologically. Areas where approaches from labor/educational studies would benefit health care research are suggested.

Iammarino, S., 2005. An evolutionary integrated view of Regional Systems of Innovation: Concepts, measures and historical perspectives. *European Planning Studies*, 13(4), pp.497–519. Available at:
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09654310500107084> [Accessed December 16, 2013].

Abstract: The literature on geographical systems of innovation has traditionally shown a “national-bias” that has strongly affected the identification of actors, relationships and attributes operating at the sub-national scale. Indeed, the historical evolution of the regional dimension has rarely been considered (implying that history really matters only at the national level). Modes of governance have also mostly

been examined from a country perspective, which neglects the complexity, heterogeneity and path dependency of multi-level governance in current innovation systems. This paper reviews the main literature on the concept of Regional Systems of Innovation (RSI), adopting an integrated view that brings together both top-down and bottom-up characteristics and evolutionary mechanisms for the purpose of identifying RSIs. After discussing conceptual problems, and the relevance and applicability of an evolutionary integrated view of RSI, the case of Italy is employed to support the argument that the historical perspective on regional cultures is often unavoidable in order to assess future opportunities for regional development.

Imbs, J. & Wacziarg, R., 2003. Stages of diversification. *The American Economic Review*, 93(1), pp.63–86. Available at:
http://www.anderson.ucla.edu/faculty_pages/romain.wacziarg/downloads/stages.pdf.

Abstract: This paper studies the evolution of sectoral concentration in relation to the level of per capita income. We show that various measures of sectoral concentration follow a U-shaped pattern across a wide variety of data sources: countries first diversify, in the sense that economic activity is spread more equally across sectors, but there exists, relatively late in the development process, a point at which they start specializing again. We discuss this finding in light of existing theories of trade and growth, which generally predict a monotonic relationship between income and diversification.

Isaksen, A., 2001. Building Regional Innovation Systems: Is Endogenous Industrial Development Possible in the Global Economy? *Canadian Journal of Regional Science*, 24(1), pp.101–120. Available at:
<http://cjrs-rcsr.org/archives/24-1/ISAKSEN.pdf>.

Abstract: This article aims to analyse some of the possibilities and barriers that local communities face in promoting endogenous industrial development in an increasingly globalised economy. The analysis is based on the view that regionalization is an important aspect of the globalisation trend and, therefore, a crucial economic trend in the international economy. In the second section, some theoretical issues are introduced and some policy background and dilemmas set out. In the third section, a description is given of the 1997 decision by the large transnational corporation, Ericsson, to move one of its development departments from a small Norwegian town to the Oslo region. The reversal of this decision caused by strong opposition from employees and the local area in general is then analysed. This example illustrates some threats that globalisation trends exert on the local economic development potential, as well as opportunities for economic development which it can create in certain areas. Finally, in the concluding section, the discussion departs from the “Ericsson case” and discusses, from the perspective of regional innovation systems, development policies aimed at embedding units of TNC in local areas. The section also discusses how the case study may advance our understanding of the interplay of globalisation and regional dynamics.

Kaiser, R. & Prange, H., 2004. The reconfiguration of National Innovation Systems—the example of German biotechnology. *Research Policy*, 33(3), pp.395–408. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733303001422> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The concept of the National System of Innovation (NSI) has been applied in order to analyze the interrelation of institutions and technological development. It has been diversified as a growing number of studies recognized the emergence of autonomous innovation systems at various territorial levels. Focusing on German biotechnology, this article takes an alternative perspective arguing that functions of the NSI became part of a multi-level governance system. By proposing a multi-level approach, which directs on the dynamic reconfiguration of NSIs towards the subnational as well as the international level, we are trying to bridge the gap between innovation system approaches that analytically highlight one specific territorial level only.

Karlsen, A., 2005. The dynamics of regional specialization and cluster formation: dividing trajectories of maritime industries in two Norwegian regions. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 17(5), pp.313–338. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/08985620500247702> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: The theoretical starting point of this paper is the academic debate on regional specialization, agglomeration and industrial clusters. The paper offers further insights into the industrial dynamics within regional contexts by combining two approaches: (1) an historical study of industrial agency focusing on entrepreneurship, diversification and specialization; (2) a study of the relations within contemporary industrial systems important for industrial upgrading. Methodical triangulation has provided longitudinal studies. Particular attention is paid to path dependence as well as entrepreneurial capacity in order to explain why the industrial trajectories of matching regions divide. As the paper discusses continuity and change, a more dynamic perspective on path dependency is introduced. The past is not just regarded as a constraint, but as heritage as well. The dynamics leading to cluster formation and upgrading as well as industrial fragmentation are investigated in detail. The developments of shipyards and related maritime industries of the two Norwegian regions compared are characterized by static continuity and dynamic continuity, respectively.

Krugman, P., 1991. Increasing returns and economic geography. *Journal of Political Economy*, 99(3), pp.483–499. Available at: http://www.princeton.edu/pr/pictures/g-k/krugman/krugman-increasing_returns_1991.pdf.

Abstract: This paper develops a simple model that shows how a country can endogenously become differentiated into an industrialized “core” and an agricultural “periphery.” In order to realize scale economies while minimizing transport costs, manufacturing firms tend to locate in the region with larger demand, but the location of demand itself depends on the distribution of manufacturing. Emergence of a core-periphery pattern depends on transportation costs, economies of scale, and the share of manufacturing in national income.

Krugman, P., 1993. On the number and location of cities. *European Economic Review*, 37(2-3), pp.293–298. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0014292193900175>.

Kuhlmann, S. & Edler, J., 2003. Scenarios of technology and innovation policies in Europe: Investigating future governance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 70(7), pp.619–637. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0040162503000271> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: In Europe, public research, technology and innovation policies are no longer exclusively in the hands of national authorities: increasingly, national initiatives are supplemented by, or even competing with, regional innovation policies or transnational programmes, in particular the activities of the European Union. At the same time, industrial innovation increasingly occurs within international networks. Are we witnessing a change of governance in European innovation policy? Based on some theoretical assumptions concerning the relationship between the “political systems” and “innovation systems” in Europe, the paper speculates about the future governance of innovation policies, trying to pave ways for empirical analyses. It sketches three scenarios stretching from (1) the idea of an increasingly centralised and dominating European innovation policy arena to (2) the opposite, i.e., a progressive decentralisation and open competition between partly strengthened, partly weakened national or regional innovation systems and finally to (3) the vision of a centrally “mediated” mixture of competition and cooperation between diverse regional innovation cultures and a related governance structure.

Legendijk, A. & Cornford, J., 2000. Regional institutions and knowledge – tracking new forms of regional development policy. *Geoforum*, 31(2), pp.209–218. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0016718599000317>.

Abstract: This paper is concerned to explore the role of concepts in regional development. It attempts to apply some of the lessons of recent work in organisational theory and science and technology studies to the field of regional development studies. Specifically, we seek to outline a social constructivist perspective on knowledge in regional development studies. One issue which this perspective raises is how convergence of organisational forms and procedures in the area of regional development has been coupled with an increasing focus on regional uniqueness.

Lanza, A., Temple, P. & Urga, G., 2003. The implications of tourism specialisation in the long run: an econometric analysis for 13 OECD economies. *Tourism Management*, 24(3), pp.315–321. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0261517702000651>.

Abstract: The paper aims to illumine the longrun impact of specialisation in tourism. It is shown that specialisation in tourism may not be deleterious for economic welfare once the terms of trade are considered. Conditions for an improvement in welfare are laid out and their existence tested by econometric methods within an almost ideal demand system formulation of tourist expenditure for 13 OECD economies. The analysis uses cointegration techniques and novel sequential break dating procedures evaluated where the time dimension is small. The values of the estimated parameters suggest that long run growth may not be harmed by tourism specialisation.

Law, M.T., 2004. Dissertation summary of “Specialization , Information , and Regulation in American Economic History.” *Journal of Economic History*, 64(2), pp.558–562.

Abstract: This dissertation concerns the role of specialization and asymmetric information in contributing to the rise of the American regulatory state in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. It consists of three essays that attempt to demonstrate how the forces of specialization created asymmetric information problems in markets for many goods and services, and how this in turn generated a potentially productive role for government regulation.

Lee, C.H., 1984. The service sector, regional specialization, and economic growth in the Victorian economy. *Journal of Historical Geography*, 10(2), pp.139–155. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0305748884901154>.

Abstract: During the Victorian period there were substantial regional variations in employment in the service industries. Explanations of economic growth in this period have been dominated by the notion that it was industry-led. If that were so, service growth would be a function of industrial growth. Testing of this thesis by econometric methods suggested that industry provided a poor explanation for variations in services, and that the main explanation was provided by variations in income. This raised other questions, since income per head in the industrial areas was generally much lower than in the less industrialized and service-oriented south of England. There is an abundance of evidence to suggest that this service-oriented regional growth was not derived from industrial development but from international trade and finance together with the consumer spending of a wealthy landed society. There was thus a substantial element of economic and spatial dualism in the Victorian economy. The role of heavy industry in Victorian growth thus needs to be revised considerably downward, and the importance of services and the South East region in particular revised considerably upward. Indeed it is by no means sure that the industrial regions provided the principal stimulus to Victorian growth: the evidence of this study would suggest otherwise.

Lee, J., 2011. Export specialization and economic growth around the world. *Economic Systems*, 35(1), pp.45–63. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0939362510000749> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper empirically investigates the extent to which technological characteristics in exports affect the patterns of trade-led economic growth across countries. Data of the Balassa index, which

captures a country's revealed comparative advantage, are obtained for industries classified by technological intensity. Regression results based on a sample of 71 countries since 1970 suggest that economies have tended to grow more rapidly when they have increasingly specialized in exporting high-technology as opposed to traditional or low-technology goods. The findings are robust to the presence of various control variables as well as the consideration of parameter heterogeneity and in the endogeneity of export structures.

Li, K. et al., 2010. Industrial Cluster, Network and Production Value Chain: a New Framework for Industrial Development Based on Specialization and Division of Labour. *Pacific Economic Review*, 15(5), pp.596–619. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1468-0106.2010.00528.x> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper develops a general equilibrium model with endogenous clusters and an endogenous network of division of labour to formalize and explore the interrelationship and rules of industrial clusters, the network of division of labour, and the economies of specialization and agglomeration in the new era of globalization and regionalization. The model suggests that institutional efficiency and competition among countries and industries will facilitate important circular effects, propelling and shaping the arrangement and allocation of industrial clusters, establishing their position in the value chain, and, consequently, determining the status of economic growth. In particular, the improvements in institutional efficiency of economic and technology systems will expand the demand for transactions and network size, which, in turn, will determine the development of cluster and network scope, as well as the position in the production value chain.

Li, X., 2009. China's regional innovation capacity in transition: An empirical approach. *Research Policy*, 38(2), pp.338–357. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733308002837> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Drawing upon regional innovation system literature, this paper estimates a stochastic frontier model to explain the increasing disparity in innovation performance between Chinese regions. The estimated results show that government support, the constitution of the R&D performers, and the regional industry-specific innovation environment are significant determinants of innovation efficiency. Due to the large difference in the firms' innovation performance across the regions, when regional innovation modes are transformed from university and research institute dominant to firm dominant, the overall innovation efficiency between regions becomes more and more disparate, which actually underlies the widening gap in regional innovation performance.

Loddo, S., 2006. Structural Funds and Regional Convergence in Italy. *Workin Papers*, 3, pp.1–35. Available at: <http://crenos.unica.it/crenos/sites/default/files/wp/06-03.pdf>.

Abstract: The lack of convergence across Italian Regions has been widely cited as an incontrovertible proof of failure of Cohesion policy. This paper aims to provide a twofold contribution to the debate on the effectiveness of Cohesion policies in Italy. Firstly, we provide an up-to-date view of convergence across Italian regions by focussing on the period covered by regional development policies carried out by European Community. The analysis reveals that poorer regions in Italy have indeed caught up with the richer regions over the period 1994-2004 and much of this convergence process has occurred towards region-specific steady states. Secondly, we consider Structural Funds as a conditioning variable in the convergence equation by using recently available data on expenditure implemented during the Second and the Third Planning Period. Our panel estimates point to a positive and significant impact of the Structural Funds on regional convergence in Italy over the period 1994-2004. When the Structural Funds are considered individually we find that the expenditure allocated by ERDF has medium term positive and significant returns while support to agriculture has short-term positive effects on growth which wane quickly. Finally, our results cast some doubt both on the (i) distributive efficiency of

resources allocated by ESF and (ii) on the effectiveness of the intervention policies in support to education, Human capital and employment.

Long, C. & Zhang, X., 2012. Patterns of China's industrialization: Concentration, specialization, and clustering. *China Economic Review*, 23(3), pp.593–612. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1043951X11000903> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper presents a few stylized facts on the patterns of China's industrialization by computing a set of multi-dimensional measures on industrial concentration, regional specialization, and clustering based on census data at the firm level in 1995 and 2004. Our results show that China's rapid industrialization is characterized by the following patterns: industries have become more spatially concentrated; regions have become increasingly specialized; and firms have become more interconnected, both within industries and within regions. In addition, the number of firms is growing faster in clustered areas than non-clustered ones. Together these patterns suggest that China's industrialization process is largely cluster-based—a phenomenon in which a large number of highly interconnected firms are located within a well-defined geographic region.

Lorentzen, J. et al., 2011. Smart specialisation and global competitiveness: Multinational enterprises and location-specific assets in Cape Town. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(12), pp.4782–4791.

Abstract: Multinational enterprises can play an important role in increasing the global competitiveness of cities through knowledge spillovers. The extent of spillovers depends on firm strategies, created assets and other local attributes. The paper focuses on six key sectors that account for a large share of the Cape Town metropolitan economy in South Africa. Forty-four lead firms were interviewed to assess knowledge flows, capabilities of firms and other actors, and reliance on local assets. Firms had relatively strong absorptive capacities in all sectors, although they had to cope with human capital constraints. Inadequate infrastructure and city governance of the economy posed additional problems. Nonetheless, there was evidence of localised knowledge spillovers which differed across sectors. The combination of opportunities for “smart specialisation” as focus for an economic strategy, requisite assets, and the in-principle option to leverage political capital and invest the City's capabilities are greater in some sectors than in others. Agro-processing, creative and design activities, retail, and tourism present more opportunities than oil and gas or construction for interventions to grow globally competitive activities in Cape Town.

Malmberg, A. & Maskell, P., 2002. The elusive concept of localization economies: towards a knowledge-based theory of spatial clustering. *Environment and Planning A*, 34(3), pp.429–449. Available at: <http://www.envplan.com/abstract.cgi?id=a3457> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: A number of possible advantages of industry agglomeration -- or spatial clustering -- have been identified in the research literature, notably those related to shared costs for infrastructure, the build-up of a skilled labour force, transaction efficiency, and knowledge spillovers leading to firm learning and innovation. We identify two shortcomings of existing research on the clustering phenomenon. First, the abundance of theoretical concepts and explanations stands in sharp contrast with the general lack of work aimed at validating these mechanisms empirically and the contradictory evidence found in recent empirical work in the field. Second, there is still a lack of a unified theoretical framework for analyzing spatial clustering. In an attempt to remedy the latter shortcoming, this paper investigates the nature of the cluster from a knowledge-creation or learning perspective. We argue for the need to establish a specific theory of the cluster where learning occupies centre stage. The basic requirements for such a theory of the cluster are discussed. Two main components of such a theory are identified: it must explain the existence of the cluster on the one hand and its internal organization on the other.

Marelli, E., 2004. Evolution of employment structures and regional specialisation in the EU. *Economic Systems*, 28(1), pp.35–59. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0939362504000214> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper investigates the differentiated employment structures of the European regions, their evolution over time and their implications for economic growth. The analysis focuses on the distribution of employment between the main productive sectors over the period 1983–1997 in 145 regions of the EU. Some clusters of regions which are structurally similar are identified. Finally, in order to show the importance of the economic structure for long-run growth, the productive structures are related to convergence in per-capita incomes. The main results show that convergence and persistence in employment structures may coexist; structural differences are greater within rather than between countries; and, finally, convergence in incomes is improved by the homogenisation of productive structures, although the industrial sector maintains a key role in the growth processes.

Marimon, R. & de Graça Carvalho, M., 2008. An open integrated and competitive European Research Area requires policy and institutional reforms, and better governance and coordination of S&T policies. , p.4.

Markusen, A., 1996. Sticky places in slippery space: a typology of industrial districts. *Economic Geography*, 72(3), pp.293–313.

Abstract: As advances in transportation and information obliterate distance, cities and regions face a tougher time anchoring income-generating activities. In probing the conditions under which some manage to remain “sticky” places in “slippery” space, this paper rejects the “new industrial district,” in either its Marshallian or more recent Italianate form, as the dominant paradigmatic solution. I identify three additional types of industrial districts, with quite disparate firm configurations, internal versus external orientations, and governance structures: a hub-and-spoke industrial district, revolving around one or more dominant, externally oriented firms; a satellite platform, an assemblage of unconnected branch plants embedded in external organization links; and the state-anchored district, focused on one or more public-sector institutions. The strengths and weaknesses of each are reviewed. The hub-and-spoke and satellite platform variants are argued to be more prominent in the United States than the other two. The findings suggest that the study of industrial districts requires a broader institutional approach and must encompass embeddedness across district boundaries. The research results suggest that a purely locally targeted development strategy will fail to achieve its goals.

Matatkova, K. & Stejskal, J., 2002. The analysis of the regional innovation systems - Czech Case. In *51st ERSR 2011 Congress (European Regional Science Association Congress). Barcelona, August 30 - September 3, 2011*. Barcelona, Spain: European Regional Science Association, pp. 1–12.

Abstract: Regional Innovation Systems (RIS) are a relatively new instrument in regional policy. This instrument was developed from National Innovation System in 1990s according to the fact that innovation was the most important for regional development. This instrument became immediately very popular among regional policy makers. However, there could be problems with its successful application in the region. In order to avoid these problems, this paper provides an overview of basic information about RIS. This paper further explores the existence and working of the Regional Innovation System in Czech Republic. We try to define the basic components by which we are able to decide if the RIS exists and if it works properly.

McCann, P., 2008. Globalization and economic geography: the world is curved, not flat. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 1(3), pp.351–370. Available at:
<http://cjres.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/cjres/rsn002> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper analyses the argument put that the world is becoming flatter from the perspective of economic geography and spatial economics. In order to do this, we consider the variety of empirical evidence available, much of which appears to be prima facie rather paradoxical. However, it is possible to reconcile all of the seemingly conflicting the evidence by adopting the argument that the global economy simultaneously exhibits trends towards both increasing globalization and localization. Cities are increasingly seen to be the critical context for growth. Using diagrams, we demonstrate that analytically the global economy is becoming even more curved.

McCann, Philip & Ortega-Argiles, R., 2013. Modern regional innovation policy. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 6(2), pp.187–216. Available at:
<http://cjres.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/cjres/rst007> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: This paper analyses the evolution of regional innovation policy into the mainstream of public policy. The paper examines the empirical and theoretical developments which have shifted much of the focus on innovation-related issues to matters of economic geography. As well as academic material we also review the literature on the subject produced by the international development institutions. In terms of policy, special attention is devoted to the role of local market failures and local institutions in explaining the importance and need for regional innovation policies, and the advent of the smart specialisation agenda is discussed. Finally, the paper discusses the current regional innovation policy tools and interventions observed around the world, which are seen by international institutions as examples of best practice.

McCann, P. & Ortega-Argiles, R., 2012. Redesigning and Reforming European Regional Policy: The Reasons, the Logic, and the Outcomes. *International Regional Science Review*, 36(3), pp.424–445. Available at: <http://irx.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0160017612463234> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: This article discusses the reforms to European Union (EU) regional development policy, or more precisely EU Cohesion Policy, which have been taking place over recent years. Following a discussion of the evolution of the policy, the changes in the rationale, the logic, the architecture, and the outcomes of the policy are examined from the start of the reform process in 2008 right up to the current context. The implications of these changes for the future functioning of the policy are examined in the context of wider impacts of globalization, institutional reform, and changing thinking in economic geography and development economics.

McCann, P. & Ortega-Argiles, R., 2013. Transforming European regional policy: a results-driven agenda and smart specialization. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 29(2), pp.405–431. Available at:
<http://oxrep.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/oxrep/grt021> [Accessed January 16, 2014].

Abstract: The paper examines the nature, rationale, and logic of the reforms to EU Cohesion Policy. A particular focus of the paper is on the concept of smart specialization and the use of this concept to help facilitate a results-oriented policy agenda. On the one hand, the arguments underpinning the reforms in part relate to modern thinking regarding the role of industrial policy. On the other hand, they also partly relate to advances in our understanding of the relationships between economic geography, technology, and institutions. At the same time, the specific features of the EU context also heavily influence the nature and logic of the changes, whereby legal and institutional matters linking Cohesion Policy to other EU policies all play an important role.

McCann, P. & Ortega-Argilés, R., 2013. Smart Specialization, Regional Growth and Applications to European Union Cohesion Policy. *Regional Studies*, Published, pp.1–12. Available at:
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343404.2013.799769> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: The aim of this paper is to achieve two objectives. Firstly, it examines the smart specialization concept and explains the challenges involved in applying this originally sectoral concept to an explicitly spatial and regional setting. Secondly, it explains the ways in which this might be achieved so as to make the concept suitable as a building block of a reformed European Union cohesion policy.

Moga, L.M. & Constantin, D.L., 2011. Specialization and Geographic Concentration of the Economic Activities in the Romanian Regions. *Journal of Applied Quantitative Methods*, 6(2), pp.12–21.

Abstract: The study of regional specialization and of concentrating the economic activities contributes to the identification of the place and role of each economic activity within the national economy and its growth potential. Thus, the possibility to emphasize the contribution brought by each economic activity to the development of each region is created. The aim of this paper is to verify relation between the evolution of the regional specialization and geographic concentration of economic activities in eight Romanian development regions. For this purpose, an empirical study of specialization and concentration was performed, at the level of the eight regions of Romania, before and after the moment of integration in the European Union.

Mollas-Gallart, J. & Salter, A., 2002. Diversity and excellence: considerations on research policy. *The IPTS Report*, 66. Available at:
<http://ipts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/home/report/english/articles/vol66/ITP1E666.html>.

Molle, W., 1996. The regional economic structure of the European Union: an analysis of long term developments. In K. Peschel, ed. *Regional growth and regional policy within the framework of European integration: Proceedings of a Conference on the Occasion of 25 Years Institute for Regional Research at the University of Kiel 1995*. Heidelberg: Physica-Verlag HD, pp. 66–86.

Abstract: In the present paper we describe the changes that have occurred in the structure of employment by branch in the regional system of the EU over the period 1950 – 1990. We have distinguished four ten-year subperiods. Moreover, for some elements of the analysis we give a forecast for the year 2000. So we span half a century.

Molotch, H., 2013. The City as a Growth Machine: Toward a Political Economy of Place. , 82(2), pp.309–332.

Abstract: A city and, more generally, any locality, is conceived as the areal expression of the interests of some land-based elite. Such an elite is seen to profit through the increasing intensification of the land use of the area in which its members hold a common interest. An elite competes with other land-based elites in an effort to have growth-inducing resources invested within its own areas as opposed to that of another. Governmental authority, at the local and nonlocal levels, is utilized to assist in achieving this growth at the expense of competing localities. Conditions of community life are largely a consequence of the social, economic, and political forces embodied in this growth machine. The relevance of growth to the interests of various social groups is examined in this context, particularly with reference to the issue of unemployment. Recent social trends in opposition to growth are described and their potential consequences evaluated.

Mora, R. & San Juan, C., 2004. Geographical specialisation in Spanish agriculture before and after integration in the European Union. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 34(3), pp.309–320. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0166046203000425> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper analyzes the evolution of agricultural product specialisation at the farm and county levels in Spain from 1979 to 1997. This period covers all the stages of the gradual implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy and the integration of the Spanish agriculture into the European Market. A

multiple product version of Theil and Finizza's indices of segregation is used to decompose farm product specialisation into county specialisation with respect to the national level and farm specialisation within counties. Using a probit specification, we test whether changes in specialisation are driven by comparative advantage at regional level or have been policy induced. Our results confirm the existence of increasing county specialisation and highlight the fact that counties which were initially more specialised in export-oriented products have shown the largest increase in specialisation.

Mora, T., Vayá, E. & Suriñach, J., 2005. Specialisation and growth: the detection of European regional convergence clubs. *Economics Letters*, 86(2), pp.181–185. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0165176504002551> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: The estimation methodology presented here proposes an optimum definition of convergence clubs. Results show that European regions with high specialisation in low-tech industries in 1985 present non-significant conditional convergence, whereas regions with lower specialisation and situated further from the core experience higher rates.

Morgan, K., 1997. The Learning Region: Institutions, Innovation and Regional Renewal. *Regional Studies*, 31(5), pp.491–503. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343409750132289> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: A potentially significant theoretical convergence is underway between the two hitherto distinct fields of innovation studies and economic geography. Through the prism of the “learning region” this paper examines some of the theoretical and policy implications of this convergence. Drawing on the work of evolutionary political economy, it highlights the significance for regional development of the interactive model of innovation. The paper then proceeds to examine the policy implication of this model by focusing, first, on a new generation of EU regional policy measures and, second, on a case study of regional innovation strategy in Wales. Finally, the paper offers a critical assessment of the distributional consequences of this strategy, posing the question: is regional innovation policy enough to address the socio-economic problems of old industrial regions?

Moulaert, F. & Sekia, F., 2003. Territorial Innovation Models: A Critical Survey. *Regional Studies*, 37(3), pp.289–302. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/003434003200065442> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper provides a critical review of the literature on territorial innovation models (industrial districts, milieux innovateurs, new industrial spaces, local production systems, etc.). The review is organized in two stages. First, the main features of each of these models and their view of innovation are compared. Second, their theoretical building blocks are reconstructed and evaluated from the point of view of conceptual clarity and analytical coherence. It is found that despite some semantic unity among the concepts used (economies of agglomeration, endogenous development, systems of innovation, evolution and learning, network organization and governance), territorial innovation models (TIMs) suffer from conceptual ambiguity. The latter is mainly a consequence of the way territorial innovation is theorized, i.e. in terms of technologically driven innovation and a business culture that is mainly instrumental to the capitalist market logic. This pressing ideological priority pushes the “conceptual flexibility” of TIMs across the border of coherent theory building.

Muller, E. & Zenker, A., 2001. Business services as actors of knowledge transformation: the role of KIBS in regional and national innovation systems. *Research Policy*, 30(9), pp.1501–1516. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733301001640>.

Abstract: Over the last years, there has been a significant increase in the attention paid to the activities of knowledge-intensive business services (KIBS). KIBS produce and diffuse knowledge, which is crucial

for innovation processes. The paper gives an overview of the role and function of KIBS in innovation systems and their knowledge production, transformation and diffusion activities. Focusing on innovation interactions between manufacturing small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and KIBS, the empirical analyses grasps KIBS position in five regional contexts. The analysis leads to the conclusion that innovation activities link SMEs and KIBS through the process of knowledge generation and diffusion.

Muntean, M. & Ancu, D., 2011. Specialization of the Romanian Economy as a Factor of Increasing Competitiveness in the International Market. In *International Conference "Risk in Contemporary Economy". XIIIth Edition, Galati, Romania, 2011*. Galati, Romania, pp. 80–87.

Abstract: A major importance in study performance of trade is presented by specialization profile, usually measured by comparative advantage. However, the specialization of a country in a particular sector can be measured by various indicators, their choice depending on many factors, so below, we present some of these indicators as they were by logically structured by different authors. Important to note is that if the product group that we identified to have relative comparative advantage with bigger share to export or import to / from EU and also in the total export and import, this is a first indication that it retains the advantage comparison, almost at all groups (with some minor exceptions). Romania exports respectively imports in large enough share to / from the European Union.

Natário, M. et al., 2012. Territorial Standards for Innovation: Analysis for the Regions of Portugal. *Revista de Estudos Regionales* 9, 95, pp.15–38.

Abstract: Competitiveness among regions and innovation dynamics are intimately related and depend on a solid and effective innovation system. This study aims to measure innovativeness in different Portuguese regions and to evaluate the nature of the innovation process and the relationship between innovativeness and its region of origin. To characterize the territorial innovation processes and to identify innovation patterns by regions, it analyzes their main distinctive factors, based on the Community Innovation Survey results for each region. Thus, it compares the Portuguese regions by verifying the existence of subjacent clusters and finding out the characteristics that distinguish the different groups of regions. The results point to the existence of four groups of regions, and the factors identified are related to the innovation process, namely objectives of innovation, sources of innovation, collaborative networks, triple helix performance, and obstacles to innovation.

Naudé, W., Bosker, M. & Matthee, M., 2010. Export Specialisation and Local Economic Growth. *The World Economy*, 33(4), pp.552–572. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1467-9701.2009.01239.x> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper aims to provide empirical evidence on whether export specialization or diversification is better for local economic growth. Using export data from 354 magisterial districts of South Africa for 1996 and 2001 we estimate spatial growth regressions that include measures of the degree of export specialization and diversification. Overall, exporting regions outperform other (less or non-) exporting regions. Also, we find that export specialisation, rather than export diversification, has been associated with local economic growth; with specialization in mining and agriculture being especially beneficial. Our results support the view that specialization in a locality's area of comparative advantage is good for local economic development. We also find that localities with higher initial levels of human capital, and higher subsequent population growth, performed better. This is consistent with the belief that policies aimed at strengthening human capital and improving agglomeration economies, will enhance local economic development.

Neffke, F., Henning, M. & Boschma, R., 2011. How Do Regions Diversify over Time? Industry Relatedness and the Development of New Growth Paths in Regions. *Economic Geography*, 87(3), pp.237–265. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1944-8287.2011.01121.x> [Accessed December 23, 2013].

Abstract: The question of how new regional growth paths emerge has been raised by many leading economic geographers. From an evolutionary perspective, there are strong reasons to believe that regions are most likely to branch into industries that are technologically related to the preexisting industries in the regions. Using a new indicator of technological relatedness between manufacturing industries, we analyzed the economic evolution of 70 Swedish regions from 1969 to 2002 with detailed plant-level data. Our analyses show that the long-term evolution of the economic landscape in Sweden is subject to strong path dependencies. Industries that were technologically related to the preexisting industries in a region had a higher probability of entering that region than did industries that were technologically unrelated to the region's preexisting industries. These industries had a higher probability of exiting that region. Moreover, the industrial profiles of Swedish regions showed a high degree of technological cohesion. Despite substantial structural change, this cohesion was persistent over time. Our methodology also proved useful when we focused on the economic evolution of one particular region. Our analysis indicates that the Linköping region increased its industrial cohesion over 30 years because of the entry of industries that were closely related to its regional portfolio and the exit of industries that were technologically peripheral. In summary, we found systematic evidence that the rise and fall of industries is strongly conditioned by industrial relatedness at the regional level.

OECD, 2011. *OECD Reviews of Regional Innovation: Regions and Innovation Policy*, OECD Publishing. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/innovation/oecdreviewsofregionalinnovationregionsandinnovationpolicy.htm>.

Abstract: *Regions and Innovation Policy* addresses the needs of national and regional governments for greater clarity on how to strengthen the innovation capacity of regions. The first part of the book examines strategies, policies and governance, explaining why regions matter, what makes smart policy mixes, and multilevel governance. The second part of the book looks at agencies, instruments and country information, showing how agencies can maximise their impact and what policy instruments work. The final chapter provides country-by-country summaries of what countries are doing.

OECD, 2008. *The Internationalisation of Business R and D: Evidence, Impacts and Implications*, OECD Publishing. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/sci-tech/theinternationalisationofbusinessrdevidenceimpactsandimplications.htm>.

Abstract: Globalization is quickly reshaping the international economic landscape, resulting in an increasing global supply of science and technology (S&T) resources and capabilities. China and India, for example, have taken their place as important players with a growing capacity for research and innovation. As global competition intensifies and innovation becomes riskier and more costly, the business sector is internationalizing knowledge-intensive corporate functions, including R&D. Firms increasingly offshore R&D activities to other countries to sense new market and technology trends worldwide. Overall, the internationalization of a firm's R&D promises substantial benefits (cost efficiency, learning potential, etc.) but also creates serious challenges for many countries (such as the loss of R&D jobs and knowledge). This report brings together the empirical evidence on the internationalization of business R&D. It analyzes trends in the offshoring of R&D, examines its drivers and motivations, and identifies implications for innovation policy. It examines the internationalization of R&D through foreign direct investment (FDI) by multinational enterprises (MNEs), which account for the bulk of business R&D in the OECD area. It also discusses complementary aspects of the global innovation landscape, such as the internationalization of science, the growing importance of international technology co-operation and the growing international mobility of researchers.

Oldřich, H., Pavel, G. & Jiří, N., 2011. Regional Innovation Strategies in the Czech Republic. *Journal of Competitiveness*, (2), pp.11–19. Available at: <http://www.cjournal.cz/files/54.pdf>.

Abstract: Lately, the concept of innovation has become a development mantra in the fierce global competition. Competition is not limited to firms; it is also relevant for territories. An observed trend which is not surprising is the number of support tools that have been developed to reinforce the position of territories and their actors in the innovation processes. Clusters and regional innovation systems are the most important of them. However, both are rather underdeveloped in the CEE countries, including the Czech Republic. Faced with this situation, a number of Czech regional authorities (Regions) took measures to stimulate the process of creating cluster and regional innovation system (RISs). Hence, strategic planning in the form of regional innovation strategies has become an overarching concept. So far, eleven Czech Regions have elaborated on RISs and analysis of these documents was the main focus of this article. The main finding of this paper is that, there is an increasing quality of RISs in the Czech Republic. Moreover, some common and some differentiated features of RISs were also identified. Consequently, the paper emphasizes numerous problems of RISs that is perceived as a key barrier towards real regional innovation system.

Ortega-Argilés, R., 2012. The Transatlantic Productivity Gap: a Survey of the Main Causes. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 26(3), pp.395–419. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1467-6419.2012.00725.x> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: During the last 2 decades, Europe's economy experienced a productivity slowdown whereas the United States (US) economy exhibited a marked acceleration. The result is that since the early 1990s the relative productivity levels between the two regions have continuously diverged, leading to a transatlantic productivity gap. Much of the explanation for this is the strong performance of the US in the so-called "new economy" or "knowledge economy" and in particular the underinvestment in R&D, and as a result, productivity and innovation has been at the forefront in the European Policy agenda. However, various explanations for the US–European Union transatlantic productivity gap suggest that the picture is rather more complex than simply the effects on, or the result of, particular technology-driven sectors.

Padmore, T. & Gibson, H., 1998. Modelling systems of innovation: II . A framework for industrial cluster analysis in regions. *Research Policy*, 26(6), pp.625–641.

Abstract: We present a model for describing and assessing the strengths and weaknesses of industrial clusters from a regional perspective. The model is a symmetrical framework combining dimensions of the Porter competitiveness 'diamond' with an equally explicit accounting of infrastructure and markets, important in a regional framework. Measures are organized under headings of Groundings, Enterprises and Markets, which gives the model its name: GEM. The characteristics of regional innovation systems are contained in the overall competitiveness framework. The GEM determinants are organized in a way that facilitates subjective scoring and allows a mapping onto a more conventional production-system structure. We have developed scoring criteria for each of the six determinants that relate to overall competitiveness of the cluster and have established an heuristic competitiveness function (GEM Assay) that captures the substitution/complementarity relationships among the determinants. We present some examples of the use of the framework and the assay in assessing regional clusters and policies for strengthening them.

Padmore, T., Schuetze, H. & Gibson, H., 1998. Modeling systems of innovation: An enterprise-centered view. *Research Policy*, 26(6), pp.605–624. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733397000395>.

Abstract: Business enterprises operate as components of what is commonly referred to as a system of innovation. The system of innovation is the context for a process of innovation that can be described in terms of the knowledge sources and flows that lead to commercial advances. In this paper, we develop a model of the innovation process and of the system of innovation in which it takes place. The model, which describes the system from the perspective of the firm or enterprise, has the following properties:

(a) it is flexible in its application but symmetrical in structure, making it easier to generalize or specialize; (b) it is simple, which helps makers and implementers of policy to visualize their role in the system; and (c) it is quantifiable, which aids comparisons among firms and among different systems of innovation. We make some applications of the new model, and show how other frameworks can be mapped onto it. In particular, we show the relationship with the European Community's model Innovation Survey and based on that, make some comments on future directions for survey instruments.

Pålshaugen, Ø., 2011. Research in action: The development of cluster specific innovation strategies in the Oslo region. In *Learning Regional Innovation: Scandinavian Models*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 120–149.

Abstract: Since the concept of “innovation system” was launched, a large number of innovation studies have been undertaken at the different levels: national level (Edquist 1997, Lundvall 1992), regional level (Asheim and Gertler 2005) and sector level (Malerba 2004). Also, cities and clusters have been analysed from an innovation system perspective (Asheim et al. 2006, Isaksen 2007). These innovation studies undertaken at different system levels have provided a huge amount of knowledge of what are important conditions for nations, regions, sectors, clusters and networks of enterprises to be innovative. Thereby, the initial conceptual models of innovation systems have also become the subjects of critique. The dynamic of this development may be characterized as a development of new, more nuanced, theoretical models of innovation on the basis of the critique of the (at any time) established models. This dynamic is still going on, and it is of great importance for the further development of innovation policy both at the national and regional level. Asheim has recently (2010) presented a comprehensive overview of important aspects of this theoretical development, with particular regard to consequences for creating improved innovation policies at the regional level. Asheim's article shows quite neatly that the content, mixture and character of, and interplay between, the different kinds of knowledge bases will differ from region to region – as will the interaction with knowledge bases and actors outside the region. Asheim's article therefore points firmly towards the need for developing what he calls more context sensitive innovation policies at the regional level.

Paluzie, E., Pons, J. & Tirado, D.A., 2001. Regional Integration and Specialization Patterns in Spain. *Regional Studies*, 35(4), pp.285–296. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400125457> [Accessed December 24, 2013].

Abstract: The aim of this paper is to analyse how economic integration in Europe has affected industrial geographical concentration in Spain and to explain the driving forces behind industry location. First, we construct regional specialization and geographical concentration indices for 50 Spanish provinces (NUTS III) and 30 industrial sectors in 1979, 1986 and 1992. Second, we carry out an econometric analysis of the determinants of the geographical concentration of industries. Our main conclusion is that there is no evidence of increasing specialization in Spain between 1979 and 1992, and that the most important determinant of Spain's economic geography is scale economies. Furthermore, traditional trade theory does not play a role in explaining the pattern of industrial concentration. Finally, inter-industry linkages have a negative effect on concentration, indicating that the opening up of the Spanish economy may have lessened the importance of being close to suppliers.

Panapanaan, V., Uotila, T. & Jalkala, A., 2013. Creation and Alignment of the Eco-innovation Strategy Model to Regional Innovation Strategy: A Case from Lahti (Päijät-Häme Region), Finland. *European Planning Studies*, Published . Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09654313.2013.774322> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: This study focuses on the importance of eco-innovation in regional innovation strategy and policy development. It is conducted to get an in-depth understanding and learning about eco-innovation

at the regional level and to draw some principles that are important in creating and aligning the eco-innovation strategy model to regional innovation strategy. The study highlights the new eco-innovation strategy model called SAMPO which was created and developed through a series of multi-stakeholder consultations which embodied the strengthening of the region's expertise—learning and knowledge-generating environment, design and innovation. These three areas of regional expertise are translated in the SAMPO model as three spearheads of innovation activities categorized as practice-based innovation, eco-design and sustainable innovation. Some principles are derived from the creation of the SAMPO model and put forward as strategic learning points in regional innovation strategy. The SAMPO model as positively acknowledged by the Päijät-Häme Regional Council, business clusters, research institutes and academic organizations may serve as a new framework that is useful in formulating and recreating eco-innovation policy in the region.

Peck, J. & Sheppard, E., 2010. Worlds Apart? Engaging with the World Development Report 2009: Reshaping Economic Geography. *Economic Geography*, 86(4), pp.331–340. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1944-8287.2010.01093.x> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: Introducing a roundtable discussion of the World Bank's World Development Report 2009: Reshaping Economic Geography, this article contextualizes the report in intellectual and political terms. It reflects on the lost opportunities for, and potential limits of, engagement between the style of New Economic Geography espoused by the World Bank and the pluralist heterodoxy of economic geography "proper," before briefly previewing the commentaries from Gillian Hart, Victoria Lawson, and Andrés Rodríguez-Pose and the response from World Bank economists Uwe Deichmann, Indermit Gill, and Chor Ching Goh.

Pike, A., Rodríguez-Pose, A. & Tomaney, J., 2007. What Kind of Local and Regional Development and for Whom? *Regional Studies*, 41(9), pp.1253–1269. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400701543355> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper asks the question, what kind of local and regional development and for whom? It examines what is meant by local and regional development, its historical context, its geographies in space, territory, place and scale and its different varieties, principles and values. The socially uneven and geographically differentiated distribution of who and where benefits and loses from particular forms of local and regional development is analysed. A holistic, progressive and sustainable version of local and regional development is outlined with reflections upon its limits and political renewal. Locally and regionally determined development models should not be developed independently of more foundational principles and values such as democracy, equity, internationalism and justice. Specific local and regional articulations are normative questions and subject to social determination and political choices in particular national and international contexts.

Pontikakis, D., Chorafakis, G. & Kyriakou, D., 2009. R&D specialization in the EU: from stylised observations to evidence-based policy. In Dimitrios Pontikakis, Dimitrios Kyriakou, & R. van Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 71–84. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Pontikakis, Dimitrios, Kyriakou, D. & Bavel, R. van (eds. ., 2009. *The Question of R&D Specialisation Perspectives and Policy Implications*, Seville: European Commission, JRC-IPTS. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Abstract: Evidence suggests that the structural composition of European industry is the reason behind many of the challenges faced by research policy in Europe. The R&D shortfall in Europe relative to key trading partners, for example, is largely due to Europe having a smaller share of its economy composed of high R&D-intensive sectors (compared to the US or Japan). Similar structurally-dependent arguments

have been made about the disciplinary specialisation of research efforts in European universities and public research institutes: efforts seem to be spread out across multiple areas failing to reach critical mass. As a result, the question of “R&D specialisation” has emerged as an issue of debate on the research policy agenda. But what is this question and why should we bother with it? To explore this question and examine its implications for policy, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) - Institute for Prospective Technological Studies (IPTS), together with Directorate General for Research (DG RTD), organised a workshop in Barcelona on 30 June 2008. This report is an edited compilation of contributions submitted by participants at this event. The question boils down to whether, for any given geographical-political entity, there are benefits to having R&D efforts concentrated (or specialised) in a limited number of thematic areas and, if so, whether (a) public funding of R&D should focus on these areas accordingly and (b) corporate R&D investment should be steered towards these areas through structural changes to the economy (and how to achieve this). Examining whether there are benefits to the specialisation of R&D implies looking at the quality (and not just the quantity) of R&D. This is a change in orientation compared to the emphasis, implied or explicit, on reaching a given target of R&D spending. Good quality R&D is productive R&D: it effectively transforms inputs into output (both measured by whatever means). And, in times of economic crisis where “bang-for-the-buck” is being emphasised, this effectiveness of R&D is as important as ever. Research on the benefits of specialisation is still in early stages, and robust evidence is scant. However, some points can already be regarded as beyond serious dispute. For example, it is clear that reaching critical mass is necessary in certain thematic areas. Unless you reach this threshold, the effectiveness of R&D efforts will be suboptimal. Yet there are limits to the benefits of specialisation, as the law of diminishin...

Porter, M.E., 1998a. Clusters and competition: new agendas for companies, governments, and institutions. In *On Competition*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press, pp. 213–303. Available at: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.199.4104&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.

Porter, M.E., 1998b. Clusters and the New Economics of Competition. *Harvard Business Review*, Nov.-Dec., pp.77–90.

Abstract: In this article, Michael Porter, the C. Christensen Professor of Business Administration at the Harvard Business School, explains how clusters foster high levels of productivity and innovation and lays out the implications for competitive strategy and economic policy. Economic geography in an era of global competition poses a paradox. In theory, location should no longer be a source of competitive advantage. Open global markets, rapid transportation, and high-speed communications should allow any company to source any thing from any place at any time. But in practice, location remains central to competition. Today’s economic map of the world is characterized by what Porter calls clusters: critical masses in one place of linked industries and institutions--from suppliers to universities to government agencies--that enjoy unusual competitive success in a particular field. The most famous examples are found in Silicon Valley and Hollywood, but clusters dot the world's landscape. Porter explains how clusters affect competition in three broad ways: first, by increasing the productivity of companies based in the area; second, by driving the direction and pace of innovation; and third, by stimulating the formation of new businesses within the cluster. Geographic, cultural, and institutional proximity provides companies with special access, closer relationships, better information, powerful incentives, and other advantages that are difficult to tap from a distance. The more complex, knowledge-based, and dynamic the world economy becomes, the more this is true. Competitive advantage lies increasingly in local things--knowledge, relationships, and motivation--that distant rivals cannot replicate.

Porter, M.E., 1996. Competitive Advantage, Agglomeration Economies, and regional Policy. *International Regional Science Review*, 19(1-2), pp.85–90.

Abstract: From different directions and traditions, there is a growing interest in the effect of location on competition and economic geography. From my work at the level of the firm and industry, I find in Markusen’s (1996) article an opportunity to engage the literature on regional development. Especially since beginning research for my book “The Competitive Advantage of Nations”, I have been interested in

how location affects competitive advantage and how firms choose headquarters locations from a strategic perspective. This article is just one piece of a remarkable body of work by Markusen, and I agree with much of her work. Here I comment on six areas in which I believe her analysis could be sharpened and the literature as a whole extended.

Price, D.J. de S., 1963. *Little Science, Big Science*, New York: Columbia University Press.

Puga, D., 2002. European regional policies in light of recent location theories. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 2(4), pp.373–406. Available at:
<http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/2.4.373>.

Abstract: Despite large regional policy expenditures, regional inequalities in Europe have not narrowed substantially over the last two decades, and by some measures have even widened. Income differences across States have fallen, but inequalities between regions within each State have risen. European States have developed increasingly different production structures. European regions have also become increasingly polarised in terms of their unemployment rates. This paper describes these trends, and discusses how recent location theories can help us to explain them and to reconsider the role of regional policies, especially transport infrastructure improvements, in such an environment.

Quah, D., 2001. ICT Clusters in Development: Theory and Evidence. *EIB Papers*, 6(1), pp.85–100.
Available at: <https://www.econstor.eu/dspace/bitstream/10419/44806/1/33074271X.pdf>.

Abstract: This paper analyzes the impact of information and communications technologies (ICT) on economic growth and agglomeration, emphasizing outcomes for regional inequality. ICT significantly displays the same features---increasing returns, knowledge spillovers---that drive both growth and agglomeration. However, in the data, cross-economy inequality has been rising for longer than has ICT been perceptibly influencing economic performance. In Europe, nation states show no special advantage in using ICT as a driver for economic growth; ICT clusters seamlessly transcend national borders.

Ricci, L.A., 1999. Economic geography and comparative advantage: Agglomeration versus specialization. *European Economic Review*, 43(2), pp.357–377.

Abstract: This paper investigates the relationship between agglomeration and specialization, and the role of comparative versus absolute advantage. A two-country three-sector model is developed, encompassing a Ricardian comparative advantage, increasing returns, product differentiation, monopolistic competition, and trade costs. Closed-form solutions are derived for the factor immobility case, while factor mobility is analyzed via comparative statics and simulations. Several interesting results arise. Economic integration may reduce or even reverse the agglomeration pattern. Agglomeration in one country reduces its specialization within the IRS industry. An increase in comparative advantage is not necessarily associated with an increase in specialization.

Roberts, P., 1993. Managing the Strategic Planning and Development of Regions: Lessons from a European Perspective. *Regional Studies*, 27(8), pp.759–768. Available at:
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343409312331347945> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Rodríguez-Pose, A. & Crescenzi, R., 2008. Research and Development, Spillovers, Innovation Systems, and the Genesis of Regional Growth in Europe. *Regional Studies*, 42(1), pp.51–67. Available at:
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400701654186> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Research on the impact of innovation on regional economic performance in Europe has fundamentally followed three approaches: (1) the analysis of the link between investment in research and development (R&D), patents, and economic growth; (2) the study of the existence and efficiency of regional innovation systems; and (3) the examination of the geographical diffusion of regional knowledge spillovers. These complementary approaches have, however, rarely been combined. Important operational and methodological barriers have thwarted any potential cross-fertilization. This paper tries to fill this gap in the literature by combining in one model R&D, spillovers, and innovation systems approaches. A multiple regression analysis is conducted for all regions of the group of 25 European Union countries (EU-25), including measures of R&D investment, proxies for regional innovation systems, and knowledge and socio-economic spillovers. This approach allows the discrimination between the influence of internal factors and external knowledge and institutional flows on regional economic growth. The empirical results highlight how the complex interaction between local and external research, on the one hand, with local and external socio-economic and institutional conditions, on the other, shapes the innovation capacity of every region. They also indicate the importance of proximity for the transmission of economically productive knowledge, as spillovers are affected by strong distance decay effects.

Rodríguez-Pose, A. & Fratesi, U., 2004. Between Development and Social Policies: The Impact of European Structural Funds in Objective 1 Regions. *Regional Studies*, 38(1), pp.97–113. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343400310001632226> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: European regional support has grown in parallel with European integration. The funds targeted at achieving greater economic and social cohesion and reducing disparities within the European Union (EU) have more than doubled in relative terms since the end of the 1980s, making development policies the second most important policy area in the EU. The majority of the development funds have been earmarked for Objective 1 regions, i.e. regions where GDP per capita is below the 75% threshold of the EU average. However, the European development policies have come under increasing criticism based on two facts: the lack of upward mobility of assisted regions; and the absence of regional convergence. This paper assesses, using cross-sectional and panel data analyses, the failure so far of European development policies to fulfil their objective of delivering greater economic and social cohesion by examining how European Structural Fund support is allocated among different development axes in Objective 1 regions. We find that, despite the concentration of development funds on infrastructure and, to a lesser extent, on business support, the returns to commitments on these axes are not significant. Support to agriculture has short-term positive effects on growth, but these wane quickly, and only investment in education and human capital - which only represents about one-eighth of the total commitments - has medium-term positive and significant returns.

Rosenfeld, S.A., 2002. *Creating Smart Systems: A guide to cluster strategies in less favoured regions*, Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/archive/innovation/pdf/guide_rosenfeld_final.pdf.

Rossi-Hansberg, E., 2005. A spatial theory of trade. *American Economic Review*, 95(5), pp.1464–1491. Available at: <http://www.princeton.edu/~erossi/SToTAER.pdf>.

Abstract: The equilibrium relationship between trade and the spatial distribution of economic activity is fundamental to the analysis of national and regional trade patterns, as well as to the effect of trade frictions. We study this relationship using a trade model with a continuum of regions, transport costs, and agglomeration effects caused by production externalities. We analyze the equilibrium specialization and trade patterns for different levels of transport costs and externality parameters. Understanding trade via the distribution of economic activity in space naturally rationalizes the evidence on border effects and the “gravity equation.”

Rusu, M., 2013. Smart Specialization a Possible Solution to the New Global Challenges. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 6(13), pp.128–136. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S221256711300124X> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Smart specialization is a new concept that has been actively promoted as a tool for the strategy Europe 2020. It is a key solution for avoiding dissipation of the EU research funds and for focusing the research, innovation, human and financial resources on those innovative sectors which are high performing, strategic from a socio-economical perspective, eco-friendly and attractive for investors. Given the novelty and complexity of this concept consideration should be given to the concept clarification, for the use of policy makers and for its effective implementation in the wood processing industry with its R&D and innovation background and economic context.

Sachwald, F., 2008. Location choices within global innovation networks: the case of Europe. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 33(4), pp.364–378. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10961-007-9057-8> [Accessed January 2, 2014].

Abstract: Rapid growth in internationalization of corporate R&D has spurred considerable interest since the 1990s. Foreign R&D is still mainly driven by the expansion of international production, but technology sourcing has become an increasingly important driver of dispersion. Actually, differences across sectors and companies tend to obscure the mix of motivations behind the development of global innovation networks. This paper distinguishes the various drivers of the international dispersion of corporate R&D in order to elaborate a typology of foreign R&D units, including in emerging countries. This typology is used to discuss the emergence of differentiated global innovation networks and the location choices by type of R&D unit. It is applied to foreign R&D projects in Europe in high and low cost countries between 2002 and 2005. It is then used to discuss the weakening attractiveness of the European Union for R&D activities and the relevant policies that countries can design to attract different types of units.

Sadler, D., 1999. Internationalization and Specialization in the European Automotive Components Sector: Implications for the Hollowing-out Thesis. *Regional Studies*, 33(2), pp.109–119. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00343409950122918> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper explores two questions: the geographical conditions associated with an altered relationship between automobile assembly and component firms in Europe; and the ways in which automotive component firms have restructured their operations on a global basis. The first section reviews the interplay between positional balance and spatial reorganization, highlighting the significance of the strategies of leading component manufacturers. These strategies are reviewed in depth in a subsequent section, which pays particular attention to processes of internationalization and specialization. A further exploratory section asks whether-in the light of these trends-a process of hollowing-out might be taking place within the European automobile industry. It is concluded that important issues to be addressed include the balance between investment flows into and out of Europe, and the extent to which component firm internationalization is aimed at serving new growth markets outside Europe.

Sandu, S., 2012. Smart Specialization Concept and the Status of Its Implementation in Romania. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 3, pp.236–242. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2212567112001463> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: Smart specialization, a relatively new concept, has been actively promoted as an important tool for the Europe 2020 Strategy. It stands as a key solution for avoiding dissipation of the EU research funds and for focusing the research, innovation, human and financial resources on those innovative sectors which are highly performant, socio-economically important or attractive for investors. Given the

novelty and complexity of this concept, more theoretical and methodological consideration should be given to further concept clarification, for the use of policy makers and for its effective implementation in various countries, each of them with its R&D and innovation background and economic context. This paper aims to survey the literature of the field in order to relieve theoretical and methodologic elements addressing their application in Romanian context, with an assessment of implementation opportunities and of necessary instruments, according to Innovation Union objectives.

Schlossstein, D.F. & Yun, J.J., 2008. Innovation cluster characteristics of Baden-Wuerttemberg and Gyeonggi-Do. *Asian Journal of Technology Innovation*, 16(2), pp.83–112. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/19761597.2008.9668658> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: This paper sketches the key dimensions of two powerful regional innovation systems, the Bonwol Siwha Industrial Cluster in Gyeonggi Province in South Korea and Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany. Previous governments in Korea had not paid much attention to empowerment and capacity building at the regional level, resulting in severe imbalances in regional innovation readiness and propensity. To address these deficits, the government in 2005 enacted a new cluster strategy across seven industrial sites. The Bonwol Siwha National Industrial Cluster is the one located in Gyeonggi Province, one of Korea's top three regional innovation systems. This cluster, now specializing in advanced materials and components, is home to 3,000 companies and over 100,000 employees. It is now presented with the challenge of transforming itself into a high-tech industrial cluster similar to Baden-Wuerttemberg. This upgrading presents a considerable policy challenge, especially to the cluster itself and the regional government. The main obstacles on this path are the lack of any major company and a recognized research university, misalignment of conceptions between SMEs and universities, and a lack of competition among the national industrial clusters.

Schwartz, M. & Hornych, C., 2008. Specialization as strategy for business incubators: An assessment of the Central German Multimedia Center. *Technovation*, 28(7), pp.436–449. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0166497208000187> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The literature on business incubators (BIs) mainly discusses findings of incubators that do not restrict themselves to specific sectors (diversified incubators). There is a strong disregard of the possible benefits arising from the concept of a sector-specialized business incubator (SBI), although this concept has become more important in recent years. In Germany, about 19% of the incubators can be characterized as being specialized. Since 1999, nearly one-third of all new BIs in Germany opened with a sector-specific focus. This study attempts to approach this research question by examining the advantages and deficiencies of this concept and to address them with empirical observations from an SBI in the city of Halle (Germany), which has an explicit sector-focus on the media industry (MI). We identify key benefits arising from such an incubator concept: (1) high-quality premises and equipment, (2) improvement of service and consultancy offerings and (3) image effects for the location. We also find deficiencies of an SBI especially regarding internal networking activities and promotion of linkages to universities. Furthermore a negative working climate impedes interaction. This study offers implications for firms, incubator managers and local policy-makers who are concerned with the instrument of an SBI.

Seppänen, S.K., 2008. Regional Innovation Systems and Regional Competitiveness: An Analysis of Competitiveness Indexes. In *DRUID-DIME Academy Winter 2008 PhD Conference on Geography, Innovation and Industrial Dynamics*. pp. 1–27. Available at: <http://www2.druid.dk/conferences/viewpaper.php?id=2033&cf=28>.

Abstract: Analysing 13 competitiveness and innovation indexes this paper examines the influence of regional innovation systems on regional competitiveness and how the main elements, operations and features of regional innovation systems have been taken into account in the indexes. The study shows that there are many indicators which can be used for the evaluation of regional innovations systems.

However, compared with the literature on regional innovation systems the indexes offer only a partial picture of the actors, structure and dynamics of regional innovation systems and their influence on regional competitiveness.

Smith, K., 2009. Specialisation and Europe's R&D performance: a note. In D. Pontikakis, D. Kyriakou, & R. van (eds. . Bavel, eds. *The question of R&D specialisation: Perspectives and policy implications*. pp. 41–44. Available at: <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC51665.pdf>.

Sölvell, Ö., Ketels, C. & Lindqvist, G., 2008. Industrial specialization and regional clusters in the ten new EU member states. *Competitiveness Review*, 18(1/2), pp.104–130. Available at: <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/10.1108/10595420810874637> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to provide an analysis of regional concentration patterns within ten new European Union (EU) member states, EU10, and make comparisons with EU15 and the US economy. Design/methodology/approach – Industrial specialization and clusters are measured as employment in the intersection between a sector (three-digit NACE data) and a particular region (NUTS 2 level), with a total of 38 sectors and 41 regions within EU10. Regional cluster size and degree of specialization is measured along 3D: absolute number of employees (>10,000 jobs is used as cut-off for a regional cluster), degree of specialization (regional sector employment is at least two times expected levels) and degree of regional market labor dominance (>3 per cent of total employment in a particular sector). Each of these three measures of cluster size, specialization and labor market focus are classified with a “star”. The largest and most specialized clusters receive three stars. Findings – EU10 exhibits 19 three-star regional clusters, which display high values for each of the three measured parameters. In addition, there are 92 two-star regional clusters and 313 one-star regional clusters. The analysis also suggests that regional concentration in EU10 is clearly lower than in the USA, and slightly lower than in the old EU member states. In a few cases – IT, biopharmaceuticals and communications equipment – where the total size of the cluster is small, and there is little historical legacy in Eastern Europe, the EU10 exhibits higher geographical concentration than EU15. Research limitations/implications – Overall, the economies of EU10 exhibit a pattern of geographical concentration close to a random distribution, i.e. the process of regional concentration and redistribution of industry is in a very early phase. If Europe is to build a more competitive economy, industrial restructuring towards larger clusters must be allowed and pushed by policy makers both at the national and EU levels. Practical implications – Policymakers must be well informed about geographical concentration patterns of industry. The research offers a consistent methodology of mapping regional clusters and geographical concentration patterns across sectors. Originality/value – This paper is the first in measuring regional concentration patterns in Europe at this fine level, and is based on a new methodology developed by Professor Michael E. Porter at Harvard University. The paper has als...

Stolpe, M., 1995. *Technology and the dynamics of specialization in open economies*, Tubingen: Mohr. Available at: <http://econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/738/3/090027574.pdf>.

Abstract: Kielen Studien, 271

Storper, M., 2010. Why do regions develop and change? The challenge for geography and economics. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 11(2), pp.333–346. Available at: <http://joeg.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/doi/10.1093/jeg/lbq033> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Explaining the growth and change of regions and cities is one of the great challenges for social science. The field of economic geography and associated economics has developed frameworks in recent years that, while tackling major questions in spatial economic development, are deficient in their ability to explain geographical develop in a causal way, and to incorporate principal forces for change.

Storz, C., 2008. Dynamics in innovation systems: Evidence from Japan's game software industry. *Research Policy*, 37(9), pp.1480–1491. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733308001182> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: In contrast to the US and recently Europe, Japan appears to be unsuccessful in establishing new industries. An oft-cited example is Japan's practical invisibility in the global business software sector. Literature has ascribed Japan's weakness – or conversely, America's strength – to the specific institutional settings and competences of actors within the respective national innovation system. It has additionally been argued that unlike the American innovation system, with its proven ability to give birth to new industries, the inherent path dependency of the Japanese innovation system makes innovation and establishment of new industries quite difficult. However, there are two notable weaknesses underlying current propositions postulating that only certain innovation systems enable the creation of new industries: first, they mistakenly confound context specific with general empirical observations. And second, they grossly underestimate – or altogether fail to examine – the dynamics within innovation systems. This paper will show that it is precisely the dynamics within innovation systems – dynamics founded on the concept of path plasticity – which have enabled Japan to charge forward as a global leader in a highly innovative field: the game software sector.

Thissen, M. & Van Oort, F., 2010. European Place-Based Development Policy and Sustainable Economic Agglomeration. *Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie*, 101(4), pp.473–480. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1467-9663.2010.00620.x> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: The inherent tension between regional equality and economic growth (efficiency) is recently much debated in the context of place based development policy and agglomeration in the European Union. A general conclusion reached in the literature is that a policy targeted at regional equality may be harmful for economic growth. Such policy therefore should be transformed in such a way that it also promotes the mobility of both people and firms and hence facilitates the possibilities of increased agglomeration. Recent insights from economic theories suggest that agglomeration externalities are not taken into account in the migration decision of firms and people, causing the dynamic urbanisation processes to not necessarily result in a (social) welfare optimum. This is even more so if other welfare effects than GDP and product variety are taken into account. Regional economic development is not sustainable if the dynamic urbanisation processes stemming from agglomeration economies do not lead to a welfare optimum. In this paper we assess the possibility of a non-sustainable regional development path. We conclude that strong additional negative externalities of growing large agglomerations are harder to prove than negative externalities of small agglomerations becoming smaller. Moreover, the size of short run negative effects that will stimulate the migration of people has not been adequately assessed. The European Union should therefore be careful in interpreting place-based costs and benefits of growing, large agglomerations at the detriment of small regions.

Todtling, F., Asheim, B. & Boschma, R., 2013. Knowledge sourcing, innovation and constructing advantage in regions of Europe. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 20(2), pp.161–169. Available at: <http://eur.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0969776412457173> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Tödting, F., Lengauer, L. & Höglinger, C., 2011. Knowledge Sourcing and Innovation in “Thick” and “Thin” Regional Innovation Systems—Comparing ICT Firms in Two Austrian Regions. *European Planning Studies*, 19(7), pp.1245–1276. Available at: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09654313.2011.573135> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: In knowledge-based sectors such as ICT innovation is seen to be as a key factor for the competitiveness of firms. Nowadays, the innovation process is regarded to be highly interactive, so companies tend to rely on both internal and external knowledge. There are arguments that the

character of knowledge and innovation links depends to a large extent on the density and the institutional setting of the respective regional innovation system (RIS). We investigate, therefore, whether firms in a metropolitan and non-metropolitan RIS exhibit different ways and patterns to source knowledge relevant for innovation. We expect that ICT companies in a metropolitan RIS such as Vienna rely to a much higher extent on local knowledge sources in particular from universities and research organizations. For firms in a non-metropolitan RIS, such as Salzburg, we expect a higher reliance on distant knowledge links with a variety of partners. At the beginning, we provide a conceptual frame, by introducing the concept of knowledge bases and a typology of knowledge links applying these to the innovation process in the ICT sector. Then we present some empirical evidence for ICT companies in the regions of Vienna, representing a metropolitan RIS with a high density of knowledge organizations and firms, and Salzburg standing for a non-metropolitan RIS with a lower size and density of such organizations. We analyse the types of knowledge sources, the channels of knowledge exchange and the spatial level of these interactions. In the final section, we will draw some policy conclusions.

Tödttling, F. & Trippel, M., 2005. One size fits all? Towards a differentiated regional innovation policy approach. *Research Policy*, 34(8), pp.1203–1219. Available at:
<http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048733305001137> [Accessed December 12, 2013].

Abstract: Innovation has moved to the foreground in regional policy in the last decade. Concrete policies were shaped by “best practice models” derived from high-tech areas and well performing regions. These are often applied in a similar way across many types of regions. Here an attempt is made to show that there is no “ideal model” for innovation policy as innovation activities differ strongly between central, peripheral and old industrial areas. In this paper we analyse different types of regions with respect to their preconditions for innovation, networking and innovation barriers. Based on this classification different policy options and strategies are developed.

Uchida, Y. & Inomata, S., 2011. Vertical Specialization at the Time of Economic Crisis. In S. Inomata, ed. *Asia Beyond the Global Economic Crisis: The Transmission Mechanism of Financial Shocks*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 70–83.

Vincenzi, M., 2011. Information Technology, Complementary Capital and the Transatlantic Productivity Divergence. In S. Allegrezza & A. Dubrocard, eds. *Internet Econometrics*. New York, USA: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 13–42.

Abstract: Since the Lisbon Summit in 2000, there has been an active debate within Europe regarding the competitiveness of the EU regional economy. While the gap in GDP per capita is not really widening according to Van Ark, it is labor productivity that is diverging. After nearly four decades of European convergence to U.S. productivity levels, labor productivity and total factor productivity trends in the U.S. and the EU began to diverge in the mid-1990s. U.S. labor and Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth accelerated, EU productivity growth did not. A large and growing literature has tied the divergence in labor productivity trends to superior American investment in and utilization of Information and Communications Technologies (ICT). More recent work has attributed some of the divergence in Total Factor Productivity to ICT as well. Superior American performance appears to arise not only or even mostly from high levels of investment in ICT; rather, American industries and firms appear to derive greater output boosts from their investment. Basu et al. (2003) have proposed a model consistent with these facts, in which the impact of ICT investment is enhanced by unmeasured investment in organizational capital that is complementary to the ICT hardware and software. In this paper, we build on the work of Basu et al., both conceptually and empirically. In our empirical work, we develop a simple model of unmeasured complementary capital and apply it to U.S., French and Belgian data in order to understand whether complementary capital accumulation can explain the “missing” TFP growth in the European countries since the mid of the 1990s. Theory suggests that TFP growth should be negatively correlated with contemporaneous investments in ICT capital, because firms are diverting resources to install the new capital; while it should be positively associated with lagged investments in ICT capital. Whereas the United States started to invest in ICT and in complementary capital in the late 1980s and

continued during all the 1990s, we find evidence that France and Belgium delayed the wave of ICT investments until the late 1990. We also trace the benefits of these late investments on TFP growth during the first years of the 21st Century. We also begin to suggest a different conceptualization of “Complementary Capital” that suggests a role for constrained supplies of skilled labor in determining the impact of ICT investment on productivity. We offer preliminary evidence suggesti...

Wren, C., 1999. Review of the book “Competitiveness, Localised Learning and Regional Development: Specialisation and Prosperity in Small Open Economies”, by Peter Maskell, Heikki Eskelinen & Ingjalundur Hannibalsson. *The Economic Journal*, 109(459), pp.F800–F802.

Yang, D. & Liu, Z., 2012a. Does farmer economic organization and agricultural specialization improve rural income? Evidence from China. *Economic Modelling*, 29(3), pp.990–993. Available at: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0264999312000429> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper builds simultaneous equations model based on survey data of 2445 Chinese villages to do empirical analysis of the relationship among farmer economic organization, agricultural specialization and rural income. It finds that raising the level of agricultural specialization can improve rural income significantly, and the development of farmer economic organization is an effective way to raise the level of agricultural specialization; The factors, which affect whether farmers participating in farmer economic organization, are characteristics of farmers, situation of farmer economic organization and relevant policies promoting the development of farmer economic organization. Therefore, it has great significance to agricultural specialization and rural income growth for government to take measures to promote development of farmer economic organization.

Yang, D. & Liu, Z., 2012b. Study on the Chinese farmer cooperative economy organizations and agricultural specialization. *Agric. Econ. – Czech*, 58(3), pp.135–146.

Abstract: Under the background of the Chinese Household Contract Responsibility System (HCRS), farmers have to pay higher transaction costs and encounter a huge trading risk if they engage in agricultural production only through the market transaction. Since the special properties of agricultural production limit the formation and development of agricultural enterprises, farmer cooperative economy organizations with the main functional characteristics of transaction coordination begin to flourish. By building a new classical economics model, this paper demonstrates the theoretical assertion that the generation of a farmer cooperative economy organization is accompanied by the evolution of the division of labour, the improvement of farmers’ effectiveness and the development of agricultural specialization. Furthermore, this paper does an empirical analysis with the micro-survey data to verify this theoretical assertion. Therefore, this article effectively explains the generation condition of a farmer cooperative economy organization and the internal mechanism of how it promotes the development of agricultural specialization. So this paper provides a strong theoretical and practical evidence for the development of a farmer cooperative economy organization and agricultural specialization.

Zhang, J., 2009. The regional specialization of service sector in China- from 1993 to 2006. In *ICSSSM '09. 6th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management*. Xiamen: IEEE, pp. 126–130. Available at: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/lpdocs/epic03/wrapper.htm?arnumber=5174868>.

Abstract: Using the Krugman index, we calculate the regional specialization of 29 provinces’ service sector in China. Further, we analyze some specific industries of the service sector through the location quotient. Then we compare the degree of specialization between each other of 10 provinces. The main conclusions of this paper are: Firstly, the average specialization of service sector is lower than manufacture sector because of the specific characteristics of service industry; Secondly, the specialization degree of service industry in China has been descending then increasing since 1990s; Thirdly, metropolitan areas have remarkable advantages in the developing of producer service industry and knowledge intensive service industry.

Zheng, D. & Kuroda, T., 2013. The impact of economic policy on industrial specialization and regional concentration of China's high-tech industries. *The Annals of Regional Science*, 50(3), pp.771–790. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00168-012-0522-4> [Accessed December 19, 2013].

Abstract: This paper uses a dynamic panel approach to investigate the impact of economic policy on industrial specialization and regional concentration of China's high-tech industries for the period 1996–2005. It is found that the degrees of specialization and concentration show increasing trends throughout the sample period, while high-tech industry sector has increasingly concentrated in coastal regions. It is also found that the implementation of high-technology-oriented export policy and subsidy for science and high-technology activities encourage specialization and concentration, whereas local governments' protection for local high-tech enterprises results in convergence in regional industrial structure and obstructs regional concentration of high-tech industries. The estimation result is robust not only to the use of various estimation techniques, but also to the control for other factors proposed by theories such as transport costs and knowledge resources. Our findings support the idea that economic policies might play an important role in determining the geographic distribution of high-tech industries in China.

Zucker, L.G., Darby, M.R. & Armstrong, J., 1998. Geographically localized knowledge: spillovers or markets? *Economic Inquiry*, 36(1), pp.65–86. Available at: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1465-7295.1998.tb01696.x> [Accessed January 14, 2014].

Abstract: Using detailed data on California biotechnology, we find that the positive impact of research universities on nearby firms relates to identifiable market exchange between particular university star scientists and firms and not to generalized knowledge spillovers. Poisson and two-stage Heckman regressions indicate the number of star-firm collaborations powerfully predicts success: for an average firm, five articles coauthored by academic stars and the firm's scientists imply about five more products in development, 3.5 more products on the market, and 860 more employees. Stars collaborating with or employed by firms, or who patent, have significantly higher citation rates than pure academic stars.